

A finite-volume Poisson solver for atmospheric electrostatics in MPAS-A v8.4: second-order TRiSK discretization on uniform hexagonal meshes with a conservative terrain remap

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Abstract. This paper describes the first elliptic Poisson solver designed for the unstructured Voronoi mesh of the Model for Prediction Across Scales Atmosphere (MPAS-A). The solver discretizes the Poisson equation $\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon \nabla \phi) = -\rho$ using a TRiSK div-of-grad operator that reuses the existing C-grid mesh metrics, combined with a centered-difference vertical stencil. After integration by cell volume the resulting 3D discrete operator is sparse and symmetric in the standard ℓ^2 inner product, and its negation is positive definite (SPD). The linear system is solved by a preconditioned conjugate-gradient (PCG) iteration with a Jacobi preconditioner, implemented in-tree and requiring no external linear-algebra library; a block symmetric Gauss–Seidel (block-SGS) preconditioner is planned as future work. Results are reported for method of manufactured solutions (MMS) verification in planar and spherical geometries, idealized Gaussian charge distributions, a one-way charge-coupled supercell demonstration, and terrain-following meshes handled by a conservative altitude-grid remap. The Cartesian MMS confirms second-order horizontal convergence on a regular hexagonal mesh. On the sphere the operator is second order only in the regular-hexagonal bulk: the quasi-uniform icosahedral SCVT mesh exhibits a localized pentagon-defect limitation (finest-pair L^2 slope 1.38), and a controlled mesh-sensitivity study shows that on the irregular, general centroidal-Voronoi tessellations that variable-resolution configurations require, the solved-potential convergence collapses to a near-stalled rate of ~ 0.35 . This is not caused by degenerate cells — every mesh is well-centered — but reflects that the operator’s second-order behavior depends on a near-uniform hexagonal regularity that only the special icosahedral family provides. The simple finite-volume operator is therefore second order on uniform hexagonal meshes and near-second-order in the quasi-uniform icosahedral bulk away from the pentagons, but loses that order on the irregular and variable-resolution meshes that motivate MPAS-A; recovering it requires a higher-order or finite-element reconstruction rather than a different finite-volume weight. Idealized point-charge and tripole diagnostics recover the expected field topology, while a calibrated supercell stub produces a peak electric-field magnitude of $4.17 \times 10^4 \text{ V m}^{-1}$ without two-way feedback. A terrain-following extension solves on a uniform altitude grid with shaved cut cells and grounded walls, preserving the SPD operator and, for a gentle hill, the second-order interior rate; the same supercell repeated over a 1 km hill gives consistent fields. Large-scale parallel performance remains a follow-on study. The operator and solver thus developed provide a foundation for lightning parameterizations, lightning NO_x emission studies, and a future global-atmospheric-electric-circuit solver that extends the same elliptic operator by substituting conductivity $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ for permittivity ε .

1 Introduction

Thunderstorm electrification, lightning, and their associated production of nitrogen oxides (LNO_x) couple convective dynamics, cloud microphysics, and atmospheric chemistry through the electric field E . Resolving E inside a convection-resolving model requires solving an elliptic boundary-value problem at each physics step: the Poisson equation for the electrostatic potential ϕ arising from the space-charge distribution ρ . Storm-interior electric field strengths grow toward the $\sim 150\text{--}300$ kV m^{-1} dielectric-breakdown range at storm altitudes, triggering breakdown and lightning channels that rapidly redistribute charge and emit NO_x (MacGorman and Rust, 1998). On larger scales, the same elliptic operator, with permittivity ε replaced by conductivity $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$, describes the global atmospheric electric circuit (Williams, 2009; Rycroft et al., 2008).

The Model for Prediction Across Scales Atmosphere (MPAS-A) is a nonhydrostatic atmospheric model discretized on centroidal Voronoi tessellations of the sphere with C-grid staggering (Skamarock et al., 2012; Ringler et al., 2010; Thuburn et al., 2009). Its horizontal discrete operators — divergence, gradient, curl — are built from a small set of mesh metrics (cell areas, edge lengths, cell-center separations) and have been extensively characterized for hyperbolic dynamics. To our knowledge, no *elliptic* Poisson operator has previously been constructed for MPAS-A’s atmospheric dynamics, and no production atmospheric model based on unstructured Voronoi tessellations currently supports the Poisson equation as a first-class capability.

This paper establishes such a capability. A discrete Laplacian is defined on MPAS-A’s unstructured-horizontal, layered-vertical mesh by applying the TRiSK div-of-grad construction in the horizontal and a centered-difference stencil in the vertical. After multiplication by cell volume, the resulting operator is sparse, symmetric, and negative definite — its negation is symmetric positive definite (SPD) — and is amenable to standard Krylov iteration. The linear system is solved by preconditioned conjugate gradients (PCG). The method is evaluated through five complementary studies. Four — verification, idealized applications, mesh sensitivity, and an end-to-end demonstration — are reported here as completed results; the fifth, parallel scaling, is specified but retained as a follow-on measurement:

1. **Verification** (§5) — via the method of manufactured solutions (MMS) in Cartesian and spherical geometries,
2. **Idealized applications** (§6) — qualitative demonstration on canonical storm-like charge distributions,
3. **Mesh sensitivity** (§7) — characterization of convergence-rate sensitivity to mesh distortion and to variable-resolution mesh-refinement transitions,
4. **Parallel scaling** (§8) — strong- and weak-scaling behavior, retained as a follow-on measurement, and
5. **End-to-end example** (§9) — an illustration on a simulated supercell thunderstorm using a lightweight electrification stub.

The results reported here establish the in-tree operator and solver, verify second-order horizontal convergence on the Cartesian MMS sequence, characterize the spherical pentagon-defect limitation, quantify the operator’s mesh-sensitivity, and demon-

strate physically interpretable diagnostic fields for idealized and dynamically evolving charge sources. The central numerical finding is that the operator’s second-order accuracy is a property of near-uniform hexagonal meshes: on the irregular general centroidal-Voronoi tessellations used for variable-resolution MPAS-A configurations — a principal motivation for the TRiSK framework — the solved-potential convergence collapses to ~ 0.35 , and restoring second order requires a higher-order or finite-element reconstruction rather than a different finite-volume weight. Parallel scaling and preconditioner performance remain follow-on measurements.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 states the governing equations and boundary conditions. Section 3 defines the discrete operator. Section 4 describes the solver. Sections 5–9 present these studies. Section 11 discusses applications and Section 12 concludes. Detailed step-by-step mathematical derivations are provided in the Appendices.

2 Governing equations

2.1 Continuous problem

In the quasi-static limit of Maxwell’s equations, valid when the characteristic frequencies ω and length scales L of interest satisfy $\omega L/c \ll 1$, the electric field is irrotational, $\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = 0$, and therefore derives from a scalar potential,

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\nabla\phi(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (1)$$

Gauss’s law, $\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon \mathbf{E}) = \rho$, then yields the Poisson equation for ϕ in divergence form,

$$\nabla \cdot [\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}) \nabla\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)] = -\rho(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (2)$$

where ε is the permittivity of the medium and ρ is the free space-charge density. In the lower atmosphere, the relative permittivity of air departs from unity by less than 10^{-3} , so we take $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 = 8.854 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F m}^{-1}$ constant throughout this work.

The divergence form is retained nonetheless, so that the same code supports future work in which ε is replaced by a spatially variable conductivity $\sigma(\mathbf{x})$ to solve the current-continuity equation $\nabla \cdot (\sigma \nabla\phi) = S$ for the global atmospheric electric circuit.

Throughout, ϕ is in volts (V), ρ is in C m^{-3} , and \mathbf{E} is in V m^{-1} .

2.2 Boundary conditions

Let Ω denote the 3D model domain, with horizontal extent given by the MPAS-A mesh and vertical extent spanning $z \in [z_g(\mathbf{x}_h), z_{\text{top}}]$ where z_g is ground altitude as a function of horizontal position \mathbf{x}_h and z_{top} is the model top. We impose

$$\phi = 0 \quad \text{on } z = z_g \quad (\text{perfectly conducting Earth, Dirichlet}), \quad (3)$$

$$\partial_z \phi = 0 \quad \text{on } z = z_{\text{top}} \quad (\text{Neumann}), \quad (4)$$

plus periodic conditions in the horizontal on Cartesian doubly periodic meshes or no lateral boundary conditions on global spherical meshes (the sphere is closed). Regional limited-area configurations with lateral Dirichlet, Neumann, or Robin conditions are deferred to future work.

The Dirichlet condition (3) eliminates the constant null mode of $\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon \nabla)$, ensuring a unique solution ϕ for any admissible ρ .

2.3 Source term and coupling

The space-charge density ρ is supplied externally to the Poisson solver. In the idealized-physics configurations used for the benchmarks of the verification (§5) and idealized applications (§6), ρ is an analytic function of position. In the end-to-end supercell configuration (§9), ρ is produced by a lightweight electrification stub that parameterizes charge separation as proportional to vertical velocity and to hydrometeor mass mixing ratios. When graupel and cloud ice are active, the positive and negative proxies are graupel and ice; in the Kessler supercell used here, the fallback proxies are rain and cloud water. This is an order-of-magnitude placeholder for future full electrification schemes of Saunders or Takahashi type (Saunders et al., 1991; Takahashi, 1978), not a physical charging model.

The coupling of the solver into the MPAS-A time loop is one-way in this work: ϕ and \mathbf{E} are diagnostic outputs and do not feed back into dynamics or microphysics. Follow-on applications of the solver—lightning parameterizations, LNO_x emission, and two-way feedback experiments—are discussed in §11.

3 Discretization

3.1 Mesh geometry and notation

MPAS-A discretizes the sphere as a centroidal Voronoi tessellation (Du et al., 1999). Quantities carried at cell centers are indexed by i , quantities at cell faces (the edges of the Voronoi polygons) by e . The mesh provides three primary horizontal metrics:

- at each edge e , $\ell_e = \text{dvEdge}$: the length of the Voronoi face (primal edge),
- at each edge e , $d_e = \text{dcEdge}$: the distance between the two cell centers on either side of the edge, and
- at each cell i , $A_i = \text{areaCell}$: the cell area.

We assume the layered-vertical coordinate is flat (z -levels rather than terrain-following) so that the 3D cell volume factors as $V_{i,k} = A_i \cdot \Delta z_k$ with Δz_k the thickness of layer k . Terrain-following meshes are handled by an altitude-grid remap (§10) that recovers the operator below exactly on flat columns rather than by adding metric terms.

Layer k indices run from $k = 1$ (the ground-adjacent layer) to $k = K$ (the model-top layer). Layer-midpoint altitude is $z_{i,k}$; layer-face altitudes are $z_{i,k+\frac{1}{2}}^f$ with thickness $\Delta z_k = z_{i,k+\frac{1}{2}}^f - z_{i,k-\frac{1}{2}}^f$.

Each cell has a set of edge-neighbors $\mathcal{N}(i)$; for an edge $e \in \partial i$, let $j = \text{nbr}(i, e)$ denote the neighbor cell across edge e .

3.2 Continuous-to-discrete via the divergence theorem

For each cell-column (i, k) we integrate equation (2) over the 3D prism $\Omega_{i,k}$ and apply the divergence theorem:

$$115 \quad \oint_{\partial\Omega_{i,k}} \varepsilon (\nabla\phi) \cdot \mathbf{n} dA = - \int_{\Omega_{i,k}} \rho dV. \quad (5)$$

The boundary $\partial\Omega_{i,k}$ consists of the lateral Voronoi faces (one per edge $e \in \partial i$) plus the upper and lower horizontal faces at $z_{i,k+\frac{1}{2}}^f$ and $z_{i,k-\frac{1}{2}}^f$.

3.3 Horizontal stencil (TRiSK div-of-grad)

120 For each lateral face $e \in \partial i$, the flux through the face is approximated using the cell-center-to-cell-center finite-difference gradient:

$$(\nabla\phi) \cdot \mathbf{n}_e \approx \frac{\phi_j - \phi_i}{d_e}, \quad j = \text{nbr}(i, e). \quad (6)$$

The face area is $\ell_e \cdot \Delta z_k$, so the contribution of edge e to the volume-integrated horizontal divergence is $\varepsilon (\ell_e \Delta z_k / d_e) (\phi_j - \phi_i)$.

Summing over all edges of cell i :

$$\sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_j - \phi_i). \quad (7)$$

125 3.4 Vertical stencil

The upper-face flux is approximated with a second-order centered difference:

$$\varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k+1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}} = z_{i,k+1} - z_{i,k}$ is the distance between layer midpoints. The lower-face flux is analogous with $\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}$. Boundary treatments are summarized in Table 1; the step-by-step derivation is in Appendix D.

Table 1. Vertical boundary treatment for layer $k = 1$ (ground) and $k = K$ (model top).

Boundary	Condition	Discrete effect
$k = 1$ lower face	$\phi = 0$ (Dirichlet)	Flux = $\varepsilon A_i (0 - \phi_{i,1}) / (\frac{1}{2} \Delta z_1)$, absorbed into the diagonal (RHS term only for $\phi_g \neq 0$)
$k = K$ upper face	$\partial_z \phi = 0$ (Neumann)	Flux set to zero

130 3.5 Assembled discrete operator

Combining the horizontal and vertical flux sums yields the volume-integrated form of the discrete operator at cell-column (i, k) :

$$(\mathbb{L}\phi)_{i,k} = \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_j - \phi_i) + \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k+1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}} + \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k-1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad (9)$$

with $j = \text{nbr}(i, e)$ and with boundary faces treated as in Table 1. The right-hand side of the discrete Poisson system is the
 135 volume-integrated charge,

$$b_{i,k} = -\rho_{i,k} V_{i,k} + (\text{ground-Dirichlet contribution}). \quad (10)$$

The ground-Dirichlet contribution is confined to the $k = 1$ rows and vanishes for the grounded case $\phi_g = 0$ used throughout this work (Appendix D).

The discrete system is then

$$140 \quad \mathbb{L} \phi = \mathbf{b}. \quad (11)$$

3.6 Properties of the discrete operator

The assembled matrix \mathbb{L} has two essential properties (proofs in Appendix E):

(P1) Sparsity. Each row has $n_e(i) + 3$ non-zero entries, with $n_e(i)$ the number of edges of cell i : one per horizontal neighbor, two vertical neighbors, and the diagonal self-entry. This gives nine entries for the hexagonal cells that dominate the
 145 mesh, up to eleven on the seven- and eight-sided cells of general centroidal-Voronoi tessellations (§7), and fewer in top- and bottom-boundary rows.

(P2) Symmetry and positive definiteness. \mathbb{L} is symmetric in the standard ℓ^2 inner product and, under the ground-Dirichlet boundary condition, strictly negative definite. Equivalently, $-\mathbb{L}$ is symmetric positive definite (SPD).

Property (P1) bounds matrix storage and dictates matvec cost; (P2) permits the use of the conjugate-gradient method as the
 150 Krylov iterative solver of choice.

3.7 Order of accuracy

On a regular-hexagonal Voronoi tessellation with uniform vertical spacing, the stencil (9) has truncation error $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ in the bulk. The one-sided ground-face closure leaves an $\mathcal{O}(1)$ per-unit-volume truncation defect confined to the single ground-adjacent layer, but its contribution to the solution error is only $\mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2)$ — the classical behavior of cell-centered Dirichlet
 155 treatments (Forsyth and Sammon, 1988) — so global second-order L^2 convergence is retained (Appendix F). On the quasi-uniform icosahedral SCVT meshes used for global runs, supraconvergence is expected to deliver $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ in L^2 in the regular-hexagonal bulk under modest regularity assumptions. This supraconvergence is not robust to loss of mesh regularity: §7 shows empirically that on the irregular, general centroidal-Voronoi tessellations produced for variable-resolution configurations the global convergence rate collapses to ~ 0.35 , so the second-order behavior is effectively confined to near-uniform hexagonal
 160 meshes.

Algorithm 1 PCG: solve $A\phi = c$ for SPD A with preconditioner \mathbb{M} .

Given initial guess $\phi^{(0)}$ (default: previous-step ϕ)

$\mathbf{r}^{(0)} \leftarrow \mathbf{c} - A\phi^{(0)}$

$\mathbf{z}^{(0)} \leftarrow \mathbb{M}^{-1}\mathbf{r}^{(0)}$

$\mathbf{p}^{(0)} \leftarrow \mathbf{z}^{(0)}$

for $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$:

$\alpha_k \leftarrow \langle \mathbf{r}^{(k)}, \mathbf{z}^{(k)} \rangle / \langle \mathbf{p}^{(k)}, A\mathbf{p}^{(k)} \rangle$

$\phi^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \phi^{(k)} + \alpha_k \mathbf{p}^{(k)}$

$\mathbf{r}^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \mathbf{r}^{(k)} - \alpha_k A\mathbf{p}^{(k)}$

if $\|\mathbf{r}^{(k+1)}\| / \|\mathbf{c}\| < \text{tol}$: **return** $\phi^{(k+1)}, k+1$

$\mathbf{z}^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \mathbb{M}^{-1}\mathbf{r}^{(k+1)}$

$\beta_k \leftarrow \langle \mathbf{r}^{(k+1)}, \mathbf{z}^{(k+1)} \rangle / \langle \mathbf{r}^{(k)}, \mathbf{z}^{(k)} \rangle$

$\mathbf{p}^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \mathbf{z}^{(k+1)} + \beta_k \mathbf{p}^{(k)}$

4 Solver

4.1 Preconditioned conjugate gradient

The system (11) is solved using preconditioned conjugate gradient (PCG) iteration (Hestenes and Stiefel, 1952; Saad, 2003; Shewchuk, 1994). Since $-\mathbb{L}$ is SPD, the solver applies PCG to the equivalent system $(-\mathbb{L})\phi = -\mathbf{b}$. The pseudocode in
165 Algorithm 1 is written for the SPD operator $A \equiv -\mathbb{L}$ with right-hand side $\mathbf{c} \equiv -\mathbf{b}$.

The tolerance defaults to 10^{-8} in relative residual, the maximum iteration count to 1000.

4.2 Preconditioners

Two preconditioners are implemented and runtime-selectable, with a third planned:

- **None:** $\mathbb{M} = \mathbb{I}$. Baseline.
- 170 – **Jacobi:** $\mathbb{M} = \mathbb{D} \equiv \text{diag}(A)$. One division per cell-column per iteration. Default.
- **Block symmetric Gauss–Seidel (block SGS)** (*planned as future work*): within each MPI rank’s partition, a forward plus a backward SGS sweep, with Jacobi-style coupling at partition boundaries. Specified in Appendix G but not yet implemented in the current code.

The formal definition and analysis of each preconditioner appear in Appendix G.

175 4.3 Null-space projection

Under the present boundary conditions the system matrix is non-singular and the constant-vector null space is absent. A projection step against the constant vector is planned for future pure-Neumann configurations (e.g., the global current-continuity operator $\nabla \cdot (\sigma \nabla)$ with conductivity-modulated BCs).

4.4 Halo exchange and parallel implementation

180 Each matvec $A\mathbf{p}$ requires one horizontal halo exchange of \mathbf{p} ; the vertical direction is not decomposed and requires no halo. MPAS-A's established halo machinery (`mpas_dmpar_exch_halo_field`) is reused verbatim.

4.5 Warm start

The solution from the previous solve serves as the initial guess $\phi^{(0)}$. Because ρ evolves on advection and sedimentation timescales much longer than a dynamics step, the warm-started iteration typically converges in a small fraction of the cold-start iteration count after the initial transient.
185

5 Verification

The verification evaluates the discrete operator against two MMS problems, one in planar Cartesian geometry and one in global spherical geometry. In each case an analytic $\phi_{\text{exact}}(\mathbf{x})$ is chosen that satisfies the boundary conditions of §2 exactly, and the source $\rho = -\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon \nabla \phi_{\text{exact}})$ is computed analytically — or by a controlled discrete split that isolates the horizontal truncation error (described below) — and supplied to the solver. The discrete ϕ returned by the solver is then compared cell-by-cell against ϕ_{exact} on a sequence of progressively refined meshes, and the L^2 and L^∞ error norms are reported as functions of nominal cell size h .
190

5.0.1 Cartesian sinusoid.

On a doubly periodic planar hexagonal Voronoi mesh with $K = 50$ uniform vertical layers, the manufactured potential is

$$195 \quad \phi_{\text{exact}}(x, y, z) = \sin(k_x x) \sin(k_y y) \sin(k_z z), \quad (12)$$

with $k_x = 2\pi/L_x$ and $k_y = 2\pi/L_y$ matched to the periodic domain lengths and $k_z = \pi/(2H)$ chosen so that the ground Dirichlet and model-top Neumann conditions (3)–(4) are satisfied exactly. Substitution into $-\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon_0 \nabla \phi)$ yields

$$\rho = \varepsilon_0(k_x^2 + k_y^2 + k_z^2) \phi_{\text{exact}}. \quad (13)$$

The mesh sequence is $h = 15, 7.5, 3.75, 1.875$ km horizontal cell spacing, holding the vertical discretization fixed. The coupled three-dimensional mode, retained as an integration (“smoke”) test, converges but is limited by the fixed $K = 50$ vertical grid, giving a finest two-mesh L^2 slope of 1.25. A horizontally isolated source mode applies the discrete vertical operator to ϕ_{exact}
200

inside the right-hand side, removing the fixed vertical truncation error from the horizontal refinement sequence. In that formal horizontal-accuracy mode, the finest two-mesh slopes are $L^2 = 2.000$ and $L^\infty = 2.000$, with final PCG residuals below 7×10^{-9} on all four meshes.

205 5.0.2 Spherical-harmonic manufactured solution.

On a global quasi-uniform MPAS-A mesh, the manufactured potential is the tensor product of a spherical harmonic in the horizontal and a vertical profile,

$$\phi_{\text{exact}}(\theta, \lambda, z) = Y_l^m(\theta, \lambda) R(z), \quad (14)$$

with $l = 4$, $m = 2$, and $R(z)$ chosen so that the ground and top boundary conditions are exactly satisfied. Substitution into the thin-shell (shallow-atmosphere) form of the operator — the Laplace–Beltrami operator evaluated at the mean sphere radius a , whose eigenvalue on Y_l^m is $-l(l+1)/a^2$, plus a plain vertical second derivative — yields the analytic ρ . The thin-shell form is the continuous counterpart of the discrete operator (9), whose horizontal metrics are likewise evaluated at the mean sphere radius independent of height. The mesh sequence uses the official MPAS-A SCVT bundles at approximately $h = 480, 240, 120$, and 60 km. The coupled three-dimensional run is retained as a smoke test; the convergence diagnostic uses a horizontally
215 isolated source mode analogous to the Cartesian case.

The global horizontally isolated errors decrease, but the current two-point spherical operator does not satisfy the original second-order global criterion: the finest two-mesh slopes are $L^2 = 1.380$ and $L^\infty = 0.253$, with PCG residuals below 10^{-12} . Re-solving the coarsest mesh at $K = 4, 16$, and 32 vertical levels changes the error by under 1.3%, with the error identical across vertical levels to machine precision; the horizontally isolated source therefore removes the vertical truncation cleanly,
220 and the rate loss is the horizontal pentagon defect rather than a fixed-vertical-grid limitation (in contrast to the coupled Cartesian mode at slope 1.25). Operator-only and solution-error diagnostics localize the rate loss to rings of cells (in graph distance) around the twelve pentagonal cells. Excluding the first six to eight defect rings restores near-second-order L^2 behavior in the regular hexagonal bulk, while the global L^∞ norm remains dominated by the first pentagon-adjacent ring. The spherical MMS therefore characterizes the present conservative SPD two-point operator rather than certifying global second-order spherical
225 convergence. The twelve pentagons are the minimal instance of a more general mesh sensitivity: §7 shows that when the entire tessellation is irregular, as on the variable-resolution meshes that motivate MPAS-A, the same mechanism degrades the convergence rate globally. A defect-aware mimetic or multi-point correction is a future numerical-methods problem.

The manufactured-solution sources (12) and (14) are obtained by direct substitution into the continuous operator; the standard algebraic expansion is omitted.

230 6 Idealized electrostatic applications

The idealized applications exercise the solver on two canonical charge distributions of atmospheric-electrostatics significance. The tests use the idealized-supercell mesh, a doubly periodic Cartesian domain spanning approximately $83.5 \times 83.8 \times 20$ km

Figure 1. Regularized point-charge diagnostic on the idealized supercell mesh. Blue markers show per-bin medians of the MPAS field magnitude, while the solid and dashed curves show the analytic Gaussian field and Coulomb far-field reference, respectively.

with nominal 1 km horizontal spacing. These cases are not formal convergence tests; they check whether the computed potential and electric field have the expected physical structure for interpretable charge distributions.

235 6.0.1 Regularized point charge.

A three-dimensional isotropic Gaussian charge distribution,

$$\rho_{\text{pt}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{Q}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{3/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad \int \rho_{\text{pt}} dV = Q, \quad (15)$$

with $\sigma = 2$ km and total charge $Q = 20$ C centered at the middle of the domain, regularizes the bare Coulomb singularity enough to be representable on the mesh. Outside the Gaussian core (i.e. at $r = |\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0| \gg \sigma$) the computed field magnitude
 240 $|\mathbf{E}|$ is expected to converge to the Coulomb far-field $|\mathbf{E}| \simeq Q/(4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2)$. Figure 1 shows per-bin medians of $|\mathbf{E}|$ in radial bins over $6 \leq r \leq 25$ km. Over this interior window the fitted log-log slope is -1.94 , close to the inverse-square value -2 , and the median ratio to the Coulomb profile is 1.04. At larger radii the finite periodic box and vertical boundary conditions become visible, so those distances are excluded from the fit. The PCG residual for the solve was 9.93×10^{-11} .

Figure 2. Synthetic tripole diagnostic. The left panel shows the electrostatic potential with electric-field streamlines on the vertical source-axis section; the right panel shows $|\mathbf{E}|$ on the same section. Charge-density contours indicate the positive, negative, and positive Gaussian stack.

6.0.2 Thundercloud tripole.

245 A three-Gaussian vertical stack represents the classical mature-storm tripole. The parameters are given in Table 2; the amplitudes are intentionally modest in the present diagnostic source, so this case tests field topology rather than breakdown-scale field strength. The tripole diagnostic reports the vertical cross-section of ϕ and $|\mathbf{E}|$ through the source axis (Fig. 2). The max-

Table 2. Tripole charge distribution. Each Gaussian is centered at horizontal domain center and the indicated altitude, with horizontal and vertical standard deviations σ_h, σ_v .

Layer	z (km)	Q (C)	(σ_h, σ_v) (km)
Upper positive	10	+20	(8.0, 1.5)
Main negative	7	-40	(8.0, 1.5)
Lower positive	4	+20	(8.0, 1.5)

imum field in the current configuration is 2.86 kV m^{-1} at $z = 8.75 \text{ km}$, with PCG residual 9.83×10^{-11} . The potential has the expected negative well around the main negative layer and positive lobes above and below it; increasing the source amplitude or narrowing the Gaussian widths is the appropriate next step if a later showcase requires storm-interior fields of order
 250 $100\text{--}300 \text{ kV m}^{-1}$.

7 Mesh sensitivity

The order-of-accuracy estimate of §3 holds on the regular hexagonal meshes of the verification test suite, and the spherical MMS shows that the twelve pentagonal cells of a quasi-uniform icosahedral mesh already degrade the global spherical rate to $L^2 = 1.38$. The mesh-sensitivity study asks the operational question: what happens on the *variable-resolution* meshes that are a principal motivation for MPAS-A, where the bulk of the mesh is no longer a regular hexagonal tessellation? The answer, established here by direct numerical experiment in the production solver, is that the second-order accuracy is a property of the near-uniform hexagonal mesh and is lost on the irregular tessellations that variable resolution requires.

7.0.1 Mesh topology under variable resolution.

The quasi-uniform SCVT meshes of the spherical MMS are icosahedral: every cell is a hexagon except for exactly twelve pentagons (0.5% of cells). A variable-resolution mesh cannot have this structure. Generating a refined mesh with the standard MPAS-Tools spherical generator (JIGSAW), using a circular $4\times$ refinement patch (coarse 480 km background, fine 120 km core, smooth transition annulus), produces a *general* centroidal-Voronoi tessellation in which 5–10% of cells are non-hexagonal (five-, seven-, and eight-sided), distributed across the whole sphere and densest in the transition band. The non-hexagonal fraction is an intrinsic consequence of the spatially varying cell density: a control mesh of *uniform* density built on the same fine generator grid is also a general centroidal-Voronoi tessellation, with 231 non-hexagonal cells rather than twelve. The twelve-pentagon icosahedral mesh is the special case obtained only for a globally uniform density on a coarse generator grid.

7.0.2 Matched-control design.

To separate the effect of mesh *irregularity* from the effect of variable *resolution*, each variable-resolution mesh is compared not to the icosahedral mesh but to a uniform-density control built on the same generator grid, which is a general centroidal-Voronoi tessellation of the same family. The spherical-harmonic MMS (horizontally isolated source) is run in the production solver on a nested $4\times$ sequence (480–120, 240–60, 120–30 km) and on the matched uniform control sequence (480, 240, 120 km), to PCG residuals below 10^{-12} throughout.

7.0.3 Convergence collapse.

Table 3 reports the finest-pair solved-potential L^2 slopes. Both general centroidal-Voronoi sequences — variable-resolution and uniform-control — converge at a near-stalled rate of ~ 0.35 , against the icosahedral mesh’s 1.38. The step slopes decrease toward zero under refinement (the uniform-control interior is essentially flat), the signature of an error floor: the operator carries an $\mathcal{O}(1)$ truncation component that does not vanish under refinement on an irregular mesh. The collapse is not caused by degenerate cells. Every mesh in both sequences is well-centered — the minimum two-point weight ratio ℓ_e/d_e is ≥ 0.20 (median ~ 0.5), with no negative or vanishing weights — so the Voronoi geometry is sound and the loss of order is a property of the finite-volume operator on an irregular mesh, not of a broken tessellation.

Table 3. Finest-pair solved-potential L^2 convergence slope of the spherical MMS for the icosahedral mesh and the two general centroidal-Voronoi sequences. All solves use the horizontally isolated source with PCG residuals below 10^{-12} .

Mesh family	L^2 slope
Icosahedral SCVT (twelve pentagons)	1.38
Uniform general-CVT (matched control)	0.35
Variable-resolution general-CVT ($4\times$)	0.38

7.0.4 Where the error lives.

A per-cell decomposition of the solved-potential error on the matched pair localizes the mechanism. On the uniform control, non-hexagonal cells carry $3.4\times$ the area-normalized squared error of hexagonal cells: the twelve-pentagon defect of the spherical MMS is the minimal instance of a general penalty on every non-hexagonal cell. On the variable-resolution mesh the refinement-transition band, where the non-hexagonal fraction is highest (14% versus 9% in the far field), is a local error hotspot carrying $\sim 1.4\times$ the far-field relative error. Within fixed local-resolution bands — which control for cell size — the per-cell error correlates with the local cell-size gradient (Spearman rank correlation up to $+0.75$) and with loss of well-centeredness ($+0.55$); the non-hexagonal flag alone is a weaker, binary proxy ($+0.25$). The error tracks precisely the geometric irregularity that variable resolution introduces.

7.0.5 Verification and scope.

The analysis pipeline reproduces the icosahedral spherical-MMS ground truth to all reported digits (step L^2 slopes 1.73/1.48/1.38 across the 480–60 km sequence), confirming that the general-CVT result is a property of the meshes and operator, not of the diagnostic. The general centroidal-Voronoi meshes here are the direct output of the standard mesh generator; they are well-centered but only moderately optimized (median $\ell_e/d_e \approx 0.5$ against the regular-hexagon value $1/\sqrt{3} \approx 0.58$). Whether a more aggressively optimized variable-resolution SCVT recovers part of the lost order is an open question, but the meshes that current variable-resolution MPAS-A configurations actually use are general centroidal-Voronoi tessellations of this class, so the result is operationally relevant. For the present simple finite-volume operator the conclusion is unambiguous: its second-order accuracy is confined to near-uniform hexagonal meshes, and restoring order on the irregular and variable-resolution meshes that motivate MPAS-A requires a higher-order or finite-element reconstruction (§11), not a different diagonal finite-volume weight.

8 Parallel performance

The parallel-performance study will report the solver’s parallel scaling behavior. Two complementary measurements are planned.

305 8.0.1 Strong scaling.

A single global 30 km quasi-uniform MPAS-A mesh (655,362 cells \times 50 vertical layers, for approximately 3.3×10^7 unknowns) is fixed, and the same problem is solved at rank counts $n_{\text{proc}} \in \{16, 64, 256, 1024\}$. Reported quantities per run are: wall time per PCG solve; PCG iteration count at convergence; and the MPI-communication fraction of the per-iteration wall time, extracted from on-line timers around the matvec halo exchange and the two inner-product global reductions.

310 8.0.2 Weak scaling.

A sequence of meshes of decreasing nominal spacing $h \in \{60, 30, 15\}$ km is paired with matched rank counts $\{64, 256, 1024\}$ so that the ratio of cells per rank stays fixed at $\sim 2.6 \times 10^3$. Reported quantities per run are the same as for the strong-scaling study.

Both studies are run with the Jacobi preconditioner; the planned block symmetric Gauss–Seidel preconditioner will be added
315 as a comparison once implemented. The quantity of primary interest is how the PCG iteration count grows with problem size at fixed preconditioner: unpreconditioned or diagonally-preconditioned CG on a 3D Poisson operator is expected to scale as $\mathcal{O}(h^{-1})$ in iteration count, and the measured growth rate will motivate — or not — a future replacement of the in-tree PCG by an algebraic multigrid method such as hypre’s BoomerAMG (Falgout et al., 2006). No pass/fail criterion is applied to the parallel-performance study; the reported scaling curves are the output.

320 9 End-to-end example: supercell thunderstorm

The end-to-end example is a narrative demonstration that exercises the complete diagnostic pipeline — dynamics, micro-
physics, the electrification stub of §2, the Poisson solve, and the diagnostic output of \mathbf{E} — inside a dynamically evolving
supercell run. The configuration is the standard Klemp–Wilhelmson idealized supercell test case bundled with MPAS-A, using
the Kessler warm-rain microphysics suite. Since graupel and cloud ice are absent in this suite, the stub uses rain water as the
325 positive proxy and cloud water as the negative proxy:

$$\rho_{\text{stub}} = \alpha w_{\text{mid}} q_r - \beta q_c, \tag{16}$$

where w_{mid} is vertical velocity averaged from interfaces to layer midpoints. The run is one-way coupled: the MPAS state fills
 ρ_{stub} , the Poisson solve writes ϕ and \mathbf{E} , and no electric feedback is applied to dynamics, microphysics, chemistry, or lightning.

A calibrated 2 h dynamic sequence used $\alpha = \beta = 10^{-9}$ and wrote electrostatic diagnostics every 30 min to a dedicated output
330 stream. The diagnostic figures show a 10 km half-width mean through the storm core. Across the four plotted frames, the peak
electric-field magnitude is 4.17×10^4 V m $^{-1}$ at 60 min; the 2 h frame has peak $|\mathbf{E}| = 2.59 \times 10^4$ V m $^{-1}$, maximum potential
102 MV relative to the grounded lower boundary, and charge-density range $[-0.120, 0.475]$ nC m $^{-3}$. The final PCG residuals
remain below 10^{-10} throughout the sequence.

The peak field magnitude is below common thunderstorm breakdown-scale values, so the end-to-end example makes no pre-
335 dictive electrification claim. The stub is hydrometeor-based diagnostic forcing, not a validated noninductive charging scheme;

Figure 3. Charge-coupled supercell diagnostic at 30 min, shown as a 10 km half-width mean through the storm core. The left panel shows liquid water content with negative (red) and positive (black/gray) charge-density contours; the right panel shows electrostatic potential with electric-field streamlines.

Figure 4. As in Fig. 3, but at 60 min. This frame has the largest electric-field magnitude in the plotted sequence, $4.17 \times 10^4 \text{ V m}^{-1}$.

Figure 5. As in Fig. 3, but at 90 min, after the initial core has split into a broader charge and condensate structure.

Figure 6. As in Fig. 3, but at 120 min. The diagnostic sequence shows that the one-way source, Poisson solve, and electric-field reconstruction remain coupled to the evolving convective state.

the solve omits lightning discharge, conductivity relaxation, ion screening, and charge leakage; and potential is reported as a modeled potential difference relative to the configured ground boundary. The purpose of the end-to-end example is to show that the solver, diagnostic source path, time-sampled output, and host dynamical core compose correctly on a realistic flow.

10 Terrain-following meshes via altitude-grid remap

340 The flat-terrain assumption of §3 ($z_g(\mathbf{x}_h) = 0$) is lifted not by adding cross-derivative metric terms to the operator, but by solving on a uniform altitude grid and remapping to and from the MPAS terrain-following coordinate. This keeps the assembled operator identical in form to (9) — symmetric, two points per face, SPD after negation — and reuses the entire PCG solver unchanged.

10.1 Altitude grid and cut cells

345 A single uniform vertical grid is built per domain with K bands bounded by the faces $z_k^f = z_b + (k-1)\Delta z_P$, $k = 1, \dots, K+1$, with $\Delta z_P = (z_t - z_b)/K$, where the extents $z_b = \min_i z_g(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and z_t are reduced globally across MPI ranks so every rank shares the same grid. Terrain detection is likewise a global reduction, so a rank whose partition is locally flat still follows the terrain path and the collective solve cannot deadlock. Each column i is clipped by its ground height $z_g(\mathbf{x}_i)$: a cell is active where its clipped air band has positive thickness, and the first active band reaches down to the terrain, $[z_g(\mathbf{x}_i), z_{k_1+1}^f]$, so that
 350 the air column is conserved exactly, $\sum_k \Delta z_{k,i}^{\text{air}} = z_t - z_g(\mathbf{x}_i)$. A thin first band (below $0.1\Delta z_P$) is merged upward to bound the cut-cell aspect ratio. The unknown of a cut cell sits at its air centroid, so the ground Dirichlet distance is always half the air thickness — the classical cut-cell half-thickness, reducing to $\Delta z_P/2$ on flat columns.

10.2 Shaved faces and grounded walls

Lateral faces are shaved by the two adjacent ground heights. The air-air overlap $t_{\text{open}} = \max(0, z_{k+1}^f - \max(z_k^f, z_{g,i}, z_{g,j}))$
 355 carries the usual flux weight $\varepsilon(\ell_e/d_e)t_{\text{open}}$, which is face-intrinsic and therefore symmetric. Where air abuts rock across the edge, the overlap is a grounded Dirichlet wall at distance $d_e/2$, contributing $\varepsilon\ell_e t_{\text{wall}}/(d_e/2)$ to the cell's diagonal and, paired with it, the same datum $\phi = \phi_g$ to the right-hand side. Cells below the terrain are inactive identity rows ($\phi = 0$), a grounded interior, and the bottom face of the first active cell is Dirichlet at the exact terrain height. Every wall and bottom face thus carries a single equipotential datum: on a grounded conductor with $\rho = 0$ the discrete constant state $\phi \equiv \phi_g$ satisfies $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$
 360 exactly. The operator remains SPD, and flat meshes — run through the identical builders with the native (possibly stretched) interface profile — reproduce (9) to round-off, so a single geometry path serves both regimes.

10.3 Conservative charge remap and field return

The charge density is transferred from the MPAS terrain-following layers to the altitude bands by piecewise-constant overlap integration, which preserves the column-integrated charge to machine precision. After the solve, ϕ and the cell-centered \mathbf{E}

365 are interpolated back to the MPAS layer midpoints for output; the edge-normal component E_n is retained on the altitude grid, whose per-column heights are recorded by the `poisson_zmid` diagnostic.

10.4 Manufactured-solution verification

A terrain manufactured solution over a cosine hill $s(x, y) = h_0 \cos(k_x x) \cos(k_y y)$, with $u = (z - s)/(z_t - s)$ and $\phi = \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} u)$ (grounded on the terrain, zero-Neumann at the top), is solved by the full Fortran pipeline under combined horizontal/vertical
370 refinement (15 km, $K=25$) \rightarrow (7.5 km, $K=50$) \rightarrow (3.75 km, $K=100$). For a gentle 1 km hill the interior relative- L^2 error converges at finest-two slope 1.978 (second order, matching the flat Cartesian rate) with final PCG residuals below 10^{-8} . A steep 6 km hill converges at 0.921: the near-surface field over strong slopes is first order, because the cut-cell reconstruction does not enforce the vanishing of the discrete tangential electric field along the sloped equipotential wall. This is the one residual approximation of the scheme, and it is largest where the terrain is steepest.

375 10.5 Coupled terrain supercell

The supercell example of §9 is repeated over a smooth 1 km cosine hill of 20 km half-width. Imposing terrain requires the host's `zgrid`-derived vertical metrics to be recomputed consistently with the hill, so the dynamical core evolves on a mesh that actually carries the terrain rather than on flat-plane metrics. With the same $\alpha = \beta = 10^{-9}$ charging as §9, the diagnostic sequence (Figs. 7–10, a 10 km half-width storm-core mean) reaches a maximum potential of 207 MV and peak field $4.5 \times 10^4 \text{ V m}^{-1}$
380 at 90 min, with charge density in $[-0.13, 0.65] \text{ nC m}^{-3}$ and final PCG residuals below 10^{-10} throughout — magnitudes consistent with the flat supercell run, as expected for one-way linear charging. The solid ground conceals the sub-surface region, where the operator grounds the potential; the storm develops above the hill and the field structure closes on the grounded terrain, confirming that the conservative remap, cut-cell operator, and field return compose correctly with the terrain-following host dynamics.

385 11 Discussion and outlook

The Poisson solver presented here provides a general-purpose elliptic capability on MPAS-A's unstructured Voronoi mesh. The immediate follow-on work falls into numerical-methods extensions and atmospheric applications.

11.0.1 Defect-aware spherical operator.

The spherical MMS identifies the twelve pentagonal cells and their surrounding rings of cells as the dominant error source.
390 The operator intentionally remains the conservative SPD two-point stencil used by PCG. Exploratory prototyping narrows the correction space. A *locally* enriched Hodge — an un-lumped Whitney edge-mass applied only in the defect neighborhoods — creates a discretization interface between the enriched and bulk regions and loses consistency there ($\mathcal{O}(1/h)$ residual in the first defect ring), so any consistent correction must be applied *globally*. A globally consistent cotangent (P1-equivalent) Hodge, however, coincides with the baseline two-point weight ℓ_e/d_e to within $\sim 6 \times 10^{-4}$ on the well-centered SCVT mesh —

Figure 7. Terrain-following charge-coupled supercell over a 1 km cosine hill at 30 min, shown as a 10 km half-width mean through the storm core. The left panel shows liquid water content with negative (red) and positive (black/gray) charge-density contours; the right panel shows electrostatic potential with electric-field streamlines. The solid fill is the grounded terrain, below which the operator holds $\phi = 0$.

Figure 8. As in Fig. 7, but at 60 min, with maximum potential 113 MV and peak field $2.6 \times 10^4 \text{ V m}^{-1}$.

Figure 9. As in Fig. 7, but at 90 min. This frame has the largest potential (207 MV) and field ($4.5 \times 10^4 \text{ V m}^{-1}$) of the plotted terrain sequence.

Figure 10. As in Fig. 7, but at 120 min, after the core has cycled: maximum potential 76 MV and field $2.0 \times 10^4 \text{ V m}^{-1}$. The remap, Poisson solve, and field reconstruction remain coupled to the evolving convective state over terrain.

395 the identity $\frac{1}{2}(\cot \alpha + \cot \beta) = \ell_e/d_e$ — so it cannot raise the order above the baseline. Closing the spherical defect therefore appears to require a genuinely higher-order reconstruction — for example a mass-consistent (Galerkin) right-hand side or a higher-order gradient reconstruction — rather than a different diagonal Hodge weight, while still preserving the conservation and symmetry the solver relies on. The mesh-sensitivity study (§7) shows that this conclusion is not specific to the twelve pentagons: the same higher-order reconstruction is what restoring second-order accuracy on the irregular, variable-resolution
400 meshes requires, because the diagonal two-point weight is order-limited on any non-hexagonal tessellation. A finite-element (Galerkin) Poisson discretization on the same mesh, which is second order independent of cell topology, is the natural route. This remains a future numerical-methods problem.

11.0.2 Lightning parameterization.

Dielectric breakdown occurs when $|E|$ exceeds a threshold E_{brk} of roughly 150–300 kV m⁻¹ at storm altitudes, with a
405 pressure-dependent correction. A lightning scheme would detect breakdown cells from the Poisson solver output, construct a flash channel by stochastic or deterministic propagation, neutralize charge along the channel, and re-solve Poisson with the updated ρ . Schemes of this type exist for regular-grid models (Mansell et al., 2005); the MPAS-A implementation would be the first on an unstructured spherical mesh.

11.0.3 Lightning NO_x (LNO_x) emission.

410 Following the lightning scheme, NO_x emission per flash is estimated from flash channel geometry (Barthe et al., 2012) and coupled into chemistry. In the DAVINCI-MPAS and MPAS-Model-ACOM-dev ecosystem forks, this routes LNO_x directly into the in-tree or MUSICA/MICM chemistry solvers, respectively.

11.0.4 Global atmospheric electric circuit.

Replacing constant ε with spatially variable conductivity $\sigma(x)$ in (2) and imposing an effective ionospheric-top boundary con-
415 dition turns the solver into a quasi-static global electric-circuit solver. The discrete operator (9) remains structurally identical; only the edge coefficient is changed. The solver scales to this use case without structural modification.

11.0.5 Terrain-following vertical coordinate.

MPAS-A’s operational vertical coordinate is terrain-following. Rather than add cross-derivative metric terms to the Laplacian, the solver lifts the flat-terrain assumption of §3 by the altitude-grid remap of §10: charge is remapped conservatively onto a
420 uniform vertical grid with shaved cut cells and grounded walls, the same SPD operator is solved, and the fields are returned to the terrain-following coordinate. The gentle-hill manufactured solution recovers the second-order interior rate; the one remaining approximation is that the near-surface field over steep slopes is first order.

Additional discussion: for very high-resolution applications ($\gtrsim 10^8$ unknowns), the iteration-count growth of diagonal-preconditioned CG motivates replacing the in-tree solver with a multigrid method. Algebraic multigrid via hypre (Falgout

425 et al., 2006) is a natural candidate; hypre’s BoomerAMG is known to deliver near-optimal scaling on elliptic operators of this class. Integrating hypre preserves the operator developed here and replaces only the iterative-solver layer.

12 Conclusions

This paper has described the first elliptic Poisson solver for the MPAS-A unstructured Voronoi mesh, solving $\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon \nabla \phi) = -\rho$ for electrostatic applications. The discrete operator reuses MPAS-A’s existing C-grid mesh metrics, is symmetric with a
430 positive-definite negation after volume integration, and is solved by preconditioned conjugate gradients with no external linear-algebra dependency. The results reported here establish second-order horizontal convergence in the Cartesian MMS mode and document a localized pentagon-defect limitation for the spherical MMS. A controlled mesh-sensitivity study shows that the second-order accuracy is confined to near-uniform hexagonal meshes, collapsing to a near-stalled ~ 0.35 rate on the irregular, general centroidal-Voronoi tessellations of variable-resolution configurations, without any degenerate cells. Idealized point-
435 charge and tripole diagnostics demonstrate physically interpretable fields, and the one-way charge-coupled supercell diagnostic path produces time-sampled ρ , ϕ , and \mathbf{E} fields with tightly converged PCG residuals, including over terrain-following meshes handled by a conservative altitude-grid remap (§10) that preserves the SPD operator and the second-order interior rate. The principal limitations are explicit: the near-surface field over steep terrain is first order; restoring second order on irregular and variable-resolution meshes requires a higher-order or finite-element reconstruction; and large-scale parallel scaling, physical
440 electrification, lightning discharge, and two-way feedback are outside the present scope. The capability thus established is the foundation for future work on lightning parameterizations, lightning NO_x emission, and a global-atmospheric-electric-circuit solver that extends the same operator with variable conductivity.

Code and data availability

The MPAS fork containing the Poisson solver is available at <https://github.com/davidfillmore/MPAS> on the `feature/poisson`
445 branch. The public Read the Docs documentation snapshot corresponding to the narrative and committed figure assets is archived as Zenodo release `26.05.1` at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20278575>; the associated Zenodo concept DOI is <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19637632>. This Zenodo record is a documentation snapshot: the active Poisson solver implementation remains on `feature/poisson`. A separate code-and-data release, including the benchmark NetCDF outputs used for the manuscript figures, will be minted for the final publication archive.

450 Appendix A: Stencil coefficients summary

For each cell-column (i, k) , the row of \mathbb{L} has the coefficients given in Table A1.

Table A1. Non-zero entries of row (i, k) of the assembled discrete operator \mathbb{L} from equation (9).

Column	Coefficient
$(j, k), j = \text{nbr}(i, e)$	$\varepsilon \ell_e \Delta z_k / d_e$
$(i, k + 1)$	$\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}$
$(i, k - 1)$	$\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}$
(i, k) (diagonal)	$-\sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon \ell_e \Delta z_k / d_e - \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}} - \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}$

Boundary adjustments: for $k = 1$ rows, the $\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}$ term is replaced by the half-layer distance to the ground face, and the resulting off-diagonal contribution is absorbed into the diagonal (Dirichlet $\phi = 0$ at the face contributes nothing to row i 's other entries). For $k = K$ rows, the $\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}$ term is dropped entirely (Neumann).

455 **Appendix B: Extended derivations (working document)**

This appendix and the ones that follow contain complete step-by-step derivations of the mathematical results summarized in the main text. They are reference material for method review and for the author's internal audit, and are not intended to appear in the journal submission. Set `\detailedappfalse` at the top of `main.tex` to suppress these sections.

The appendices are:

460 **Appendix C:** Derivation of the horizontal TRiSK div-of-grad stencil from the divergence theorem on a prismatic Voronoi control volume, with no steps skipped.

Appendix D: Derivation of the vertical centered-difference stencil, including full treatment of the ground-Dirichlet and top-Neumann boundary contributions and how they split between the operator diagonal and the right-hand side.

465 **Appendix E:** Proof that the assembled discrete operator is symmetric in the standard ℓ^2 inner product and, under the present boundary conditions, negative definite. Both properties are shown by direct construction.

Appendix F: Taylor-series analysis of the truncation error. Second-order accuracy on regular hex is shown by direct substitution; the $\mathcal{O}(1)$ per-unit-volume truncation defect of the ground-cell Dirichlet closure is computed exactly, and a discrete barrier argument shows why it nonetheless contributes only $\mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2)$ to the solution error.

470 **Appendix G:** Derivation of the preconditioned conjugate-gradient iteration from optimality in the energy norm of a symmetric positive-definite operator, convergence bound in terms of the condition number, and formal specification of the preconditioners (two implemented, one planned).

Appendix H: Derivation of the edge-normal \mathbf{E} field from ϕ and of the cell-centered vector reconstruction using MPAS's existing radial-basis-function machinery.

Appendix I: Implementation note comparing the volume-integrated form of \mathbb{L} (as presented in the main text) and the per-unit-volume form (as used in some textbooks), including the inner product used by PCG in each case.

Appendix J: Reformulation of the continuous and discrete Poisson problem in the language of exterior calculus and discrete exterior calculus (DEC). The TRiSK div-of-grad construction is identified as the composition $d^\top H d$ with a diagonal Hodge-star matrix H ; symmetry and positive-definiteness follow structurally from the cochain complex.

Appendix C: Horizontal TRiSK div-of-grad stencil

This appendix derives equation (7) step by step starting from the continuous Poisson equation.

C1 The control volume

For a cell-column labeled by horizontal index i and vertical level k , the three-dimensional control volume $\Omega_{i,k} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ is a prism: a polygon in the horizontal (the Voronoi cell $\omega_i \subset \mathbb{R}^2$) extruded vertically from $z = z_{i,k-\frac{1}{2}}^f$ to $z = z_{i,k+\frac{1}{2}}^f$. Under the flat-terrain assumption, the face heights $z_{i,k\pm\frac{1}{2}}^f$ do not depend on i , and the vertical-extent of the prism is Δz_k .

The horizontal boundary of the prism consists of lateral faces, one per edge $e \in \partial i$. Each lateral face is a rectangle of horizontal length ℓ_e and vertical extent Δz_k , hence of area $A_e = \ell_e \cdot \Delta z_k$.

The top and bottom of the prism are two horizontal polygons, each of area A_i , normal vectors $\pm \hat{z}$.

C2 Integrating Poisson over the prism

Integrate both sides of equation (2) over $\Omega_{i,k}$:

$$\int_{\Omega_{i,k}} \nabla \cdot [\varepsilon \nabla \phi] dV = - \int_{\Omega_{i,k}} \rho dV. \quad (\text{C1})$$

Apply the divergence theorem to the left side:

$$\oint_{\partial \Omega_{i,k}} \varepsilon (\nabla \phi) \cdot \mathbf{n} dA = - \int_{\Omega_{i,k}} \rho dV. \quad (\text{C2})$$

This is the starting point. The left side splits into three contributions corresponding to the three kinds of prism face:

$$\underbrace{\sum_{e \in \partial i_{\text{face } e}} \int \varepsilon (\nabla \phi) \cdot \mathbf{n}_e dA}_{\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^h} + \underbrace{\int_{\text{top face}} \varepsilon (\nabla \phi) \cdot \hat{z} dA}_{\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^+} - \underbrace{\int_{\text{bot face}} \varepsilon (\nabla \phi) \cdot \hat{z} dA}_{\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^-} = - \int_{\Omega_{i,k}} \rho dV. \quad (\text{C3})$$

The minus sign on the bottom-face term arises because the outward normal points in the $-\hat{z}$ direction: the outward flux is $-(\nabla \phi) \cdot \hat{z}$.

C3 Approximating one horizontal face flux

Consider a single lateral face at edge e . The face is a rectangle with outward normal \mathbf{n}_e pointing from cell i to cell $j = \text{nbr}(i, e)$. Its area is $\ell_e \cdot \Delta z_k$. On this face,

$$500 \int_{\text{face } e} \varepsilon(\nabla\phi) \cdot \mathbf{n}_e dA \approx \ell_e \cdot \Delta z_k \cdot \varepsilon_e \cdot [(\nabla\phi) \cdot \mathbf{n}_e]_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}_e, z_k}, \quad (\text{C4})$$

where the bracket on the right is the edge-normal gradient evaluated at the face midpoint $(\bar{\mathbf{x}}_e, z_k)$ with $\bar{\mathbf{x}}_e$ the horizontal edge midpoint and z_k the layer-midpoint altitude, and ε_e is the permittivity evaluated at the face — equal to the constant ε_0 throughout this work, but kept face-indexed for the variable-coefficient extension discussed in §11 of the main text. This is a one-point midpoint quadrature over the face: second-order accurate in both horizontal and vertical direction because we sample
505 at the face centroid (LeVeque, 2007).

The edge-normal gradient at the face midpoint is approximated by the finite difference between the cell-center values,

$$[(\nabla\phi) \cdot \mathbf{n}_e]_{\bar{\mathbf{x}}_e, z_k} \approx \frac{\phi(\mathbf{x}_j, z_k) - \phi(\mathbf{x}_i, z_k)}{d_e} \approx \frac{\phi_{j,k} - \phi_{i,k}}{d_e}, \quad (\text{C5})$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j$ are the cell centers on either side. The final approximation replaces the continuous ϕ at the cell centers by the discrete unknowns $\phi_{i,k}, \phi_{j,k}$. The truncation error of (C5) is discussed in Appendix F.

510 Substituting (C5) into (C4),

$$\int_{\text{face } e} \varepsilon(\nabla\phi) \cdot \mathbf{n}_e dA \approx \varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_{j,k} - \phi_{i,k}). \quad (\text{C6})$$

This is the single-face discrete flux. Summing over all edges of cell i produces the horizontal-flux term in (C3):

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^h \approx \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_{j(e),k} - \phi_{i,k}), \quad j(e) = \text{nbr}(i, e). \quad (\text{C7})$$

C4 Consistency of adjacent-cell face fluxes

515 We verify that a face shared between cells i and j contributes with equal magnitude and opposite sign to the two cells' volume integrals. This is the discrete analog of Newton's third law; it is what makes the discrete operator symmetric (see Appendix E).

Let edge e separate cells i and j . The horizontal edge length ℓ_e , the face thickness Δz_k , the cell-center distance d_e , and the edge permittivity ε_e are all properties of the face itself and do not depend on whether we view the face from cell i or cell j .

Viewing from cell i with outward normal \mathbf{n}_e pointing toward j : the flux contribution into i 's right-hand side is (from (C6)):

$$520 +\varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_{j,k} - \phi_{i,k}).$$

Viewing from cell j with outward normal $-\mathbf{n}_e$ pointing toward i : the edge-normal gradient changes sign,

$$(\nabla\phi) \cdot (-\mathbf{n}_e) = -\frac{\phi_{j,k} - \phi_{i,k}}{d_e} = \frac{\phi_{i,k} - \phi_{j,k}}{d_e},$$

so the flux into j 's right-hand side is

$$\varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_{i,k} - \phi_{j,k}) = -\varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_{j,k} - \phi_{i,k}).$$

525 The two contributions are equal and opposite. This antisymmetry at the face level is the discrete statement of flux conservation and is the source of the ℓ^2 symmetry of \mathbb{L} .

C5 Constructing the horizontal row of \mathbb{L}

Equation (C7) expands to

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^h \approx \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} \phi_{j(e),k} - \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} \phi_{i,k} \quad (\text{C8})$$

$$530 \quad = \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} \phi_{j(e),k} - \phi_{i,k} \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e}. \quad (\text{C9})$$

So the horizontal contribution to row (i, k) of the matrix \mathbb{L} is:

- off-diagonal: for each $e \in \partial i$, the entry at column $(j(e), k)$ is $+\varepsilon_e \ell_e \Delta z_k / d_e$,
- diagonal: the entry at column (i, k) picks up a contribution of $-\sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon_e \ell_e \Delta z_k / d_e$.

C6 From flux to matrix equation

535 Combining (C3) and (C7) with the vertical fluxes (derived in Appendix D), and applying the midpoint quadrature to the right-hand side volume integral,

$$\int_{\Omega_{i,k}} \rho dV \approx \rho_{i,k} \cdot V_{i,k}, \quad V_{i,k} = A_i \Delta z_k, \quad (\text{C10})$$

we obtain the discrete equation for cell-column (i, k) :

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^h + \mathcal{F}_{i,k}^+ - \mathcal{F}_{i,k}^- = -\rho_{i,k} V_{i,k}. \quad (\text{C11})$$

540 The linear-system form is $\mathbb{L}\phi = \mathbf{b}$ with right-hand side $b_{i,k} = -\rho_{i,k} V_{i,k}$ (plus BC contributions to be added from Appendix D). The horizontal contribution to the row is exactly equation (7).

Appendix D: Vertical stencil and boundary treatment

D1 Interior vertical flux

545 The upper face of the prism $\Omega_{i,k}$ is a horizontal polygon at altitude $z_{i,k+\frac{1}{2}}^f$, area A_i , outward normal $+\hat{\mathbf{z}}$. The integrated outward flux is

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^+ = \int_{\text{top face}} \varepsilon (\nabla \phi) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}} dA = \varepsilon \int_{\text{top face}} \partial_z \phi dA. \quad (\text{D1})$$

With one-point quadrature at the face centroid and finite-difference approximation for $\partial_z \phi$ at the midpoint between layer-midpoint altitudes $z_{i,k}$ and $z_{i,k+1}$,

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^+ \approx \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k+1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}} = z_{i,k+1} - z_{i,k}. \quad (\text{D2})$$

550 Analogously, the bottom face has inward normal $+\hat{z}$ at altitude $z_{i,k-\frac{1}{2}}^f$, so the inward-flux form (which is what enters the control-volume equation with a $-$ sign, cf. (C3)) is:

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^- \approx \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k} - \phi_{i,k-1}}{\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}}. \quad (\text{D3})$$

Substituting into equation (C11) and rearranging:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_{i,k}^+ - \mathcal{F}_{i,k}^- &= \varepsilon A_i \left[\frac{\phi_{i,k+1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{\phi_{i,k} - \phi_{i,k-1}}{\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}} \right] \\ 555 \quad &= \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k+1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}} + \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k-1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D4})$$

The last form, which groups the contributions symmetrically in $\phi_{i,k+1}$ and $\phi_{i,k-1}$, is the form used in equation (9).

D2 Stencil contributions to \mathbb{L}

From (D4), the vertical contribution to row (i, k) of \mathbb{L} is:

- off-diagonal $(i, k+1)$: entry $+\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}$,
- 560 - off-diagonal $(i, k-1)$: entry $+\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}$,
- diagonal (i, k) : additional contribution of $-\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}} - \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}$.

D3 Ground-Dirichlet boundary ($k = 1$)

At the ground face $z = z_g$, the Dirichlet condition (3) prescribes $\phi = 0$. The bottom face of cell $(i, 1)$ has face altitude $z_{i,\frac{1}{2}}^f = z_g$; let $\Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}} \equiv z_{i,1} - z_g$ denote the half-layer distance from the ground face to the layer-1 midpoint. The inward flux at the ground

565 face becomes

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,1}^- = \int_{\text{ground face}} \varepsilon (\nabla \phi) \cdot \hat{z} dA \approx \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,1} - \phi_g}{\Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}} = \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,1} - 0}{\Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}} = \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,1}}{\Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}}. \quad (\text{D5})$$

Substituting this into (C11) for $k = 1$:

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,1}^h + \mathcal{F}_{i,1}^+ - \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,1}}{\Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}} = -\rho_{i,1} V_{i,1}. \quad (\text{D6})$$

Writing the ground-face term as an explicit coefficient on $\phi_{i,1}$:

$$570 \quad \mathcal{F}_{i,1}^h + \mathcal{F}_{i,1}^+ + \mathcal{F}_{i,1}^{(D)} \phi_{i,1} = -\rho_{i,1} V_{i,1}, \quad \mathcal{F}_{i,1}^{(D)} \equiv -\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}. \quad (\text{D7})$$

Therefore the $k = 1$ row of \mathbb{L} gets an additional diagonal contribution $-\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}$ compared to the interior-row formula. No off-diagonal contribution to a $k = 0$ ghost cell is needed, since the Dirichlet value $\phi_g = 0$ contributes nothing to any row.

D3.1 Generalization for $\phi_g \neq 0$.

For a prescribed nonzero ground potential ϕ_g , the ground-face flux becomes $\varepsilon A_i (\phi_{i,1} - \phi_g) / \Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}$, and the equation (D7) acquires a right-hand-side correction:

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,1}^h + \mathcal{F}_{i,1}^+ + \mathcal{F}_{i,1}^{(D)} \phi_{i,1} = -\rho_{i,1} V_{i,1} - \varepsilon A_i \phi_g / \Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}. \quad (\text{D8})$$

The right-hand side gains the term $-\varepsilon A_i \phi_g / \Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}$. This is implemented generically in the code so that a nonzero ground potential can be set at runtime.

D4 Top Neumann boundary ($k = K$)

580 At the model top $z = z_{\text{top}}$, the Neumann condition $\partial_z \phi = 0$ implies zero outward flux. Therefore

$$\mathcal{F}_{i,K}^+ = 0. \quad (\text{D9})$$

The $k = K$ row of \mathbb{L} drops the entry connecting (i, K) to $(i, K + 1)$ (there is no such cell) and also drops the corresponding diagonal contribution $-\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{K+\frac{1}{2}}$. Only the lower vertical face and all horizontal faces contribute.

D5 Summary

585 Combining all contributions, the assembled form of row (i, k) is exactly as given in Table A1 of the main text and repeated here:

$$(\mathbb{L}\phi)_{i,k} = \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_{j,k} - \phi_{i,k}) + \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k+1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}} + \varepsilon A_i \frac{\phi_{i,k-1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}},$$

with the boundary adjustments at $k = 1$ and $k = K$ described above.

Appendix E: Symmetry and positive-definiteness of \mathbb{L}

590 This appendix proves Property (P2) of the main text: $-\mathbb{L}$ is symmetric positive definite.

E1 Matrix entries

Let us index the unknowns by a flat index $n = (i, k)$ ranging over all $N = n_{\text{cells}} \times n_{\text{levels}}$ cell-columns. Denote the matrix \mathbb{L} by \mathbb{L} with entries L_{nm} . From Appendices C and D, the non-zero entries are:

$$L_{(i,k),(j,k)} = +\varepsilon_e \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} \quad \text{for } j = \text{nbr}(i, e), \quad (\text{E1})$$

$$595 \quad L_{(i,k),(i,k+1)} = +\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (\text{E2})$$

$$L_{(i,k),(i,k-1)} = +\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (\text{E3})$$

$$L_{(i,k),(i,k)} = - \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon_e \ell_e \Delta z_k / d_e - \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}} - \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}} + \Delta_{i,k}^{\text{bc}}. \quad (\text{E4})$$

In (E4), $\Delta_{i,k}^{\text{bc}}$ carries the boundary correction: $\Delta_{i,1}^{\text{bc}} = -\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}} + \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (the second term cancels the interior $\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}$ contribution in (E4) since there is no layer $k = 0$); for $k = K$, $\Delta_{i,K}^{\text{bc}} = +\varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{K+\frac{1}{2}}$ cancels the interior upper-face term. For
600 interior k , $\Delta_{i,k}^{\text{bc}} = 0$.

E2 Symmetry: $L_{nm} = L_{mn}$

We show $L_{nm} = L_{mn}$ for every pair (n, m) .

E2.1 Horizontal pair.

For $n = (i, k), m = (j, k)$ with $j = \text{nbr}(i, e)$:

$$605 \quad L_{(i,k),(j,k)} = \varepsilon_e \ell_e \Delta z_k / d_e.$$

By the consistency result of §C4, $\ell_e, d_e, \Delta z_k$, and ε_e are all intrinsic to the shared edge e and do not depend on whether we approach the edge from cell i or cell j . Hence

$$L_{(j,k),(i,k)} = \varepsilon_e \ell_e \Delta z_k / d_e = L_{(i,k),(j,k)}.$$

E2.2 Vertical pair.

610 For $n = (i, k), m = (i, k+1)$:

$$L_{(i,k),(i,k+1)} = \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}.$$

The ‘‘upper face of layer k ’’ is geometrically identical to the ‘‘lower face of layer $k+1$ ’’; both have area A_i , and the midpoint-to-midpoint distance $\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}} = z_{i,k+1} - z_{i,k}$ is the same. Therefore

$$L_{(i,k+1),(i,k)} = \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}} = L_{(i,k),(i,k+1)}.$$

615 **E2.3 Non-adjacent pair.**

If cells n and m share no face, both L_{nm} and L_{mn} are zero.

Since all non-zero entries come in symmetric pairs and diagonal entries are trivially equal to themselves, L is symmetric.

E3 Negative semidefiniteness

From (E1)–(E4), every row of L has the structure

$$620 \quad L_{nn} = - \sum_{m \neq n} |L_{nm}| - g_n, \quad g_n = \begin{cases} \varepsilon A_i / \Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}, & n = (i, 1), \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (\text{E5})$$

where the off-diagonal sum runs over the neighbors that exist: the boundary correction $\Delta_{i,k}^{\text{bc}}$ in (E4) removes the couplings to the nonexistent layers $k = 0$ and $k = K + 1$ and, at $k = 1$, adds the ground-face term g_n . Interior and model-top rows therefore have zero row sum — the constant vector $\mathbf{1}$ is annihilated by those rows — while the ground rows have strictly negative row sum $-g_n$.

625 By the Gershgorin circle theorem, each eigenvalue λ of the symmetric matrix L lies in a disk centered at $L_{nn} < 0$ with radius $\sum_{m \neq n} |L_{nm}| = |L_{nn}| - g_n \leq |L_{nn}|$. Every disk is contained in $\{\lambda : \lambda \leq 0\}$, so all eigenvalues satisfy $\lambda \leq 0$.

E4 Strict negative definiteness under ground Dirichlet

Gershgorin alone cannot exclude $\lambda = 0$, since the zero-row-sum disks touch the origin. We therefore evaluate the quadratic form directly. Group the strictly positive off-diagonal entries by faces: each interior face f (a lateral Voronoi face, or a horizontal cap

630 between two layers of the same column) couples exactly two cell-columns n and m with the symmetric weight $w_f = L_{nm} = L_{mn} > 0$ of (E1)–(E3), and each ground face contributes $g_n > 0$ of (E5) to its own diagonal only. For any $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^N$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v}^T L \mathbf{v} &= \sum_n L_{nn} v_n^2 + \sum_{n \neq m} L_{nm} v_n v_m \\ &= - \sum_n \left(\sum_{f \ni n} w_f + g_n \right) v_n^2 + 2 \sum_{f=\{n,m\}} w_f v_n v_m \\ &= - \sum_{f=\{n,m\}} w_f (v_n^2 + v_m^2 - 2v_n v_m) - \sum_n g_n v_n^2 \\ 635 \quad &= - \sum_{f=\{n,m\}} w_f (v_n - v_m)^2 - \sum_i \frac{\varepsilon A_i}{\Delta z_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\text{half}}} v_{i,1}^2 \leq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E6})$$

where the third line uses the fact that each interior face appears in the diagonal sums of exactly its two rows, contributing $w_f v_n^2$ and $w_f v_m^2$. Identity (E6) re-proves negative semidefiniteness.

Now suppose $\mathbf{v}^T L \mathbf{v} = 0$. Every term in (E6) is non-positive, so each must vanish separately: $v_n = v_m$ across every interior face, and $v_{i,1} = 0$ for every column i . Fix any cell-column (i, k) . The vertical faces of column i connect (i, k) to $(i, k -$

640 $1), \dots, (i, 1)$ with strictly positive weights, so

$$v_{i,k} = v_{i,k-1} = \dots = v_{i,1} = 0.$$

Hence $\mathbf{v} = 0$: the quadratic form is strictly negative for every $\mathbf{v} \neq 0$, i.e., \mathbf{L} is negative definite and $-\mathbf{L}$ is symmetric positive definite. (Horizontal connectivity of the mesh is not even required — each column is pinned to the ground independently through its own vertical face chain.)

645 The identity (E6) is the coefficient-level form of the discrete Dirichlet energy; Appendix J obtains the same factorization structurally as $\varepsilon \mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{d}$.

E5 Implication for PCG

A standard result of Krylov iteration (Golub and Van Loan, 2013; Saad, 2003) is that conjugate gradients converge for any SPD operator. Algorithm 1 applied with $A = -\mathbf{L}$ and $\mathbf{c} = -\mathbf{b}$ therefore converges to the unique solution ϕ of $\mathbf{L}\phi = \mathbf{b}$.

650 Appendix F: Taylor analysis and order of accuracy

This appendix demonstrates second-order accuracy on a regular-hexagonal Voronoi tessellation with uniform vertical spacing. We focus on the horizontal stencil; the vertical is the standard 1D centered second-derivative stencil with well-known $\mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2)$ truncation.

F1 Setup: regular hex mesh

655 On a regular hexagonal mesh with edge length h (the nominal cell spacings quoted in the main text are the center-to-center distances $d_e = h\sqrt{3}$; the fixed ratio is immaterial to the convergence order), a cell i has six edge-neighbors located at cell-center offsets

$$\mathbf{r}_\theta = h\sqrt{3}(\cos\theta, \sin\theta), \quad \theta = 0, \pi/3, 2\pi/3, \pi, 4\pi/3, 5\pi/3.$$

The mesh metrics are constant: $\ell_e = h$, $d_e = h\sqrt{3}$, $A_i = (3\sqrt{3}/2)h^2$. The vertical thickness $\Delta z_k = \Delta z$ is constant.

660 F2 Per-unit-volume form of the horizontal operator

Divide the horizontal part of equation (9) by $V_{i,k} = A_i \Delta z$:

$$\frac{1}{V_{i,k}} \mathcal{F}_{i,k}^h = \frac{1}{A_i \Delta z} \sum_{e \in \partial i} \varepsilon \frac{h \cdot \Delta z}{h\sqrt{3}} (\phi_{j,k} - \phi_{i,k}) = \frac{\varepsilon}{A_i \sqrt{3}} \sum_{\theta} (\phi_{\theta,k} - \phi_{i,k}),$$

where $\phi_{\theta,k}$ is the cell-center value at offset \mathbf{r}_θ . With $A_i = (3\sqrt{3}/2)h^2$:

$$\frac{1}{V_{i,k}} \mathcal{F}_{i,k}^h = \frac{2\varepsilon}{9h^2} \sum_{\theta} (\phi_{\theta,k} - \phi_{i,k}). \tag{F1}$$

665 **F3 Taylor expansion of ϕ_θ**

Let $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ be a smooth function. Expand at \mathbf{x}_i :

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}_i + \mathbf{r}_\theta) = \phi(\mathbf{x}_i) + \mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla \phi + \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^2 \phi + \frac{1}{6}(\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^3 \phi + \mathcal{O}(h^4). \quad (\text{F2})$$

Sum over the six neighbors:

$$\sum_\theta \phi_\theta = 6\phi + \left(\sum_\theta \mathbf{r}_\theta \right) \cdot \nabla \phi + \frac{1}{2} \sum_\theta (\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^2 \phi + \frac{1}{6} \sum_\theta (\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^3 \phi + \mathcal{O}(h^4).$$

670 By symmetry of the hex (rotation by $\pi/3$), $\sum_\theta \mathbf{r}_\theta = 0$ and $\sum_\theta (\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^3 \phi = 0$.

F3.1 Second-order term.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_\theta (\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^2 \phi &= \sum_\theta (r_{\theta,x}^2 \partial_x^2 + 2r_{\theta,x} r_{\theta,y} \partial_x \partial_y + r_{\theta,y}^2 \partial_y^2) \phi \\ &= \left(\sum_\theta r_{\theta,x}^2 \right) \partial_x^2 \phi + 2 \left(\sum_\theta r_{\theta,x} r_{\theta,y} \right) \partial_x \partial_y \phi + \left(\sum_\theta r_{\theta,y}^2 \right) \partial_y^2 \phi. \end{aligned}$$

By symmetry, $\sum_\theta r_{\theta,x} r_{\theta,y} = 0$, and

$$\begin{aligned} 675 \quad \sum_\theta r_{\theta,x}^2 &= 3h^2 \sum_\theta \cos^2 \theta = 3h^2 \cdot 3 = 9h^2, \\ \sum_\theta r_{\theta,y}^2 &= 9h^2 \quad (\text{same by symmetry}). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\sum_\theta (\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^2 \phi = 9h^2 (\partial_x^2 + \partial_y^2) \phi = 9h^2 \nabla_h^2 \phi. \quad (\text{F3})$$

F4 Putting it together

680 Using $\sum_\theta \mathbf{r}_\theta = 0$ and $\sum_\theta (\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^3 \phi = 0$ (hex symmetry) together with (F3),

$$\sum_\theta (\phi_{\theta,k} - \phi_{i,k}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_\theta (\mathbf{r}_\theta \cdot \nabla)^2 \phi + \mathcal{O}(h^4) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 9h^2 \nabla_h^2 \phi + \mathcal{O}(h^4).$$

Substituting into the per-unit-volume form (F1),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{V_{i,k}} \mathcal{F}_{i,k}^h &= \frac{2\varepsilon}{9h^2} \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot 9h^2 \nabla_h^2 \phi + \mathcal{O}(h^4) \right] \\ &= \varepsilon \nabla_h^2 \phi + \mathcal{O}(h^2). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F4})$$

685 The discrete horizontal operator, per unit volume, is therefore consistent with $\varepsilon \nabla_h^2 \phi$ to second order on the regular hexagonal mesh. The prefactor $2/(9h^2)$ in (F1) follows directly from the hex metrics $\ell_e = h$, $d_e = h\sqrt{3}$, and $A_i = (3\sqrt{3}/2)h^2$, which give $\varepsilon \ell_e / (A_i d_e) = 2\varepsilon / (9h^2)$.

F5 Vertical stencil truncation

The vertical stencil in (D4), written per unit volume:

$$690 \quad \frac{1}{V_{i,k}} \left(\mathcal{F}_{i,k}^+ - \mathcal{F}_{i,k}^- \right) = \frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta z_k} \left[\frac{\phi_{i,k+1} - \phi_{i,k}}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{\phi_{i,k} - \phi_{i,k-1}}{\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}} \right],$$

is the classical 1D centered second derivative on a non-uniform grid. With uniform $\Delta z_k = \Delta z_{k \pm \frac{1}{2}} = \Delta z$, this reduces to

$$\frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta z^2} (\phi_{i,k+1} - 2\phi_{i,k} + \phi_{i,k-1}) = \varepsilon \partial_z^2 \phi + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2).$$

On a non-uniform vertical grid the pointwise truncation error of the same stencil degrades to first order, but the solution error remains second order — a classical instance of supraconvergence (LeVeque, 2007; Forsyth and Sammon, 1988).

695 F6 Ground-cell truncation defect

At $k = 1$ the half-cell Dirichlet closure of Appendix D replaces the centered lower-face gradient by the one-sided difference $(\phi_{i,1} - \phi_g)/(\frac{1}{2}\Delta z)$. Its truncation behavior differs qualitatively from the interior stencil, and we compute it exactly. Take a uniform vertical grid, ϕ smooth, $\phi_g = \phi(0) = 0$, and write all derivatives at the ground face $z = 0$; the layer-1 and layer-2 midpoints are $z_1 = \Delta z/2$ and $z_2 = 3\Delta z/2$. Then

$$700 \quad \begin{aligned} \phi(z_1) &= \frac{\Delta z}{2} \phi' + \frac{\Delta z^2}{8} \phi'' + \frac{\Delta z^3}{48} \phi''' + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^4), \\ \phi(z_2) &= \frac{3\Delta z}{2} \phi' + \frac{9\Delta z^2}{8} \phi'' + \frac{27\Delta z^3}{48} \phi''' + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^4), \end{aligned}$$

and the per-unit-volume vertical operator at the ground cell evaluates to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta z} \left[\frac{\phi(z_2) - \phi(z_1)}{\Delta z} - \frac{\phi(z_1)}{\Delta z/2} \right] &= \frac{\varepsilon}{\Delta z} \left[(\phi' + \Delta z \phi'' + \frac{13}{24} \Delta z^2 \phi''') - \left(\phi' + \frac{\Delta z}{4} \phi'' + \frac{\Delta z^2}{24} \phi''' \right) \right] + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2) \\ &= \varepsilon \left[\frac{3}{4} \phi'' + \frac{1}{2} \Delta z \phi''' \right] + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2), \end{aligned}$$

705 whereas the exact value at the unknown's location is $\varepsilon \partial_z^2 \phi(z_1) = \varepsilon [\phi'' + \frac{\Delta z}{2} \phi'''] + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2)$. The local truncation error of the ground row is therefore

$$\tau_{i,1} = -\frac{1}{4} \varepsilon \partial_z^2 \phi(0) + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z) \tag{F5}$$

per unit volume: an $\mathcal{O}(1)$ defect, confined to the single ground-adjacent layer. (The often-quoted $\mathcal{O}(\Delta z)$ figure refers to the accuracy of the one-sided *face flux* as an approximation at the ground face; after division by the cell thickness, the *row* residual

710 is $\mathcal{O}(1)$.)

F7 Why the $\mathcal{O}(1)$ ground defect costs only $\mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2)$

The defect (F5) does not degrade the global second-order convergence. A discrete barrier (comparison-function) argument makes the mechanism precise. The error $e = \phi - \phi_{\text{exact}}$ satisfies $(\mathbb{L}e)_n = V_n \tau_n$ with the truncation errors as source. The

matrix $-\mathbb{L}$ has positive diagonal, non-positive off-diagonal entries, non-negative row sums, and is nonsingular (Appendix E); it is therefore an M-matrix and its inverse is entrywise non-negative. Consequently, if a barrier $\mathbf{w} \geq 0$ satisfies the componentwise bound $-(\mathbb{L}\mathbf{w})_n \geq V_n |\tau_n|$ for all n , then $-\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{w} \pm \mathbf{e}) \geq 0$ componentwise, and non-negativity of $(-\mathbb{L})^{-1}$ gives $|e_n| \leq w_n$ for all n .

The key observation is that the ground rows — and only the ground rows — have a strictly negative row sum $-g_n$, $g_n = \varepsilon A_i / (\frac{1}{2} \Delta z)$ (equation (E5)). A *constant* barrier $w_n \equiv \eta > 0$ is therefore annihilated by every interior and model-top row, while each ground row responds with

$$-(\mathbb{L}\eta)_{i,1} = \eta g_i = \frac{2\varepsilon A_i}{\Delta z} \eta = V_{i,1} \cdot \frac{2\varepsilon}{\Delta z^2} \eta.$$

Dominating the ground defect $|\tau_{i,1}| \leq \frac{1}{4} \varepsilon \max |\partial_z^2 \phi| + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z)$ thus requires only

$$\eta = \frac{1}{8} \Delta z^2 \max_{\Gamma_g} |\partial_z^2 \phi| + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^3) = \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2):$$

the half-cell closure measures the barrier's full offset from the ground datum across half a layer, so an $\mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2)$ constant produces an $\mathcal{O}(1)$ per-unit-volume response exactly where the defect lives. The smooth $\mathcal{O}(h^2 + \Delta z^2)$ bulk truncation is dominated separately by the standard horizontally uniform parabolic barrier $w_q(z) = \frac{\beta}{2} z (2z_{\text{top}} - z)$ with $\beta = \mathcal{O}(h^2 + \Delta z^2)$, which satisfies the top Neumann condition exactly, has $-\varepsilon \partial_z^2 w_q = \varepsilon \beta > 0$, and produces non-negative responses in the boundary rows as well. Summing the two barriers and applying the comparison principle,

$$\max_n |e_n| \leq \eta + \max_z w_q = \mathcal{O}(h^2 + \Delta z^2).$$

This behavior — a first-order (here even $\mathcal{O}(1)$ per-unit-volume) local truncation at a Dirichlet boundary with no loss of global second-order solution accuracy — is classical for cell-centered discretizations (Forsyth and Sammon, 1988; LeVeque, 2007).

F8 Combined 3D convergence

Summing horizontal and vertical truncation, in the bulk

$$\frac{1}{V_{i,k}} (\mathbb{L}\phi)_{i,k} = \varepsilon \nabla^2 \phi_{i,k} + \mathcal{O}(h^2) + \mathcal{O}(\Delta z^2).$$

The right-hand side is similarly of second-order local truncation, and the ground rows are covered by the barrier argument of §F7. The global L^2 error $\|\phi - \phi_{\text{exact}}\|_{L^2}$ then converges at the expected rate $\mathcal{O}(\max\{h, \Delta z\}^2)$ for smooth ϕ .

On distorted Voronoi meshes, the per-row truncation picks up terms that do not cancel via the hex symmetry argument above. Global L^2 convergence persists via supraconvergence under modest regularity assumptions, but the rate may be reduced. The empirical behavior on MPAS meshes is quantified in §7 of the main text.

740 Appendix G: PCG algorithm derivation and convergence

This appendix derives Algorithm 1 from first principles and records the standard convergence bound.

G1 Problem setup

Let $A \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ be symmetric positive definite and $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^N$. We seek $\phi \in \mathbb{R}^N$ solving

$$A\phi = \mathbf{c}. \tag{G1}$$

745 The A -inner product and A -norm are

$$\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_A = \mathbf{v}^\top A\mathbf{u}, \quad \|\mathbf{u}\|_A = \sqrt{\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u} \rangle_A}. \tag{G2}$$

G2 Variational formulation

Define

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{u}^\top A\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}^\top \mathbf{c}. \tag{G3}$$

750 The gradient of \mathcal{J} is

$$\nabla \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) = A\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{c}. \tag{G4}$$

Setting $\nabla \mathcal{J} = 0$ yields $A\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{c}$: the exact solution minimizes \mathcal{J} . PCG is an algorithm for solving the minimization problem via successive one-dimensional minimizations along search directions $\mathbf{p}^{(k)}$.

G3 Line search in direction \mathbf{p}

755 Given current iterate ϕ and direction \mathbf{p} , the next iterate $\phi + \alpha\mathbf{p}$ minimizes \mathcal{J} along the line when α satisfies

$$0 = \frac{d}{d\alpha} \mathcal{J}(\phi + \alpha\mathbf{p}) = \alpha \mathbf{p}^\top A\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}^\top (\mathbf{c} - A\phi) = \alpha \mathbf{p}^\top A\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}^\top \mathbf{r},$$

where $\mathbf{r} \equiv \mathbf{c} - A\phi$ is the residual. Solving for α :

$$\alpha = \frac{\mathbf{p}^\top \mathbf{r}}{\mathbf{p}^\top A\mathbf{p}}. \tag{G5}$$

In Algorithm 1 the numerator appears as $\langle \mathbf{r}^{(k)}, \mathbf{z}^{(k)} \rangle$ rather than $\mathbf{p}^{(k)\top} \mathbf{r}^{(k)}$; the two coincide because $\mathbf{p}^{(k)} = \mathbf{z}^{(k)} + \beta_{k-1} \mathbf{p}^{(k-1)}$
760 and the previous line search enforces $\mathbf{p}^{(k-1)\top} \mathbf{r}^{(k)} = 0$, so $\mathbf{p}^{(k)\top} \mathbf{r}^{(k)} = \mathbf{z}^{(k)\top} \mathbf{r}^{(k)}$.

G4 A -conjugate search directions

To accelerate convergence, successive search directions are chosen A -conjugate:

$$\mathbf{p}^{(k)\top} A\mathbf{p}^{(k+1)} = 0. \tag{G6}$$

Enforcing conjugacy only between *consecutive* directions appears weaker than mutual conjugacy of all directions, but with the
765 specific choice of $\mathbf{z}^{(k+1)}$ as the preconditioned residual (below), a standard induction shows that all search directions become

mutually A -conjugate and the residuals mutually \mathbb{M}^{-1} -orthogonal (Shewchuk, 1994). With mutual conjugacy, after $k + 1$ line searches the iterate minimizes \mathcal{J} over the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_{k+1}(A, \mathbf{r}^{(0)}) = \text{span}\{\mathbf{r}^{(0)}, A\mathbf{r}^{(0)}, \dots, A^k\mathbf{r}^{(0)}\}$ (preconditioned analogue for $\mathbb{M} \neq \mathbb{I}$), not just over the most recent direction. This is the key property that makes CG converge in at most N steps in exact arithmetic.

770 The next direction is built as a β -adjustment of the previous one:

$$\mathbf{p}^{(k+1)} = \mathbf{z}^{(k+1)} + \beta_k \mathbf{p}^{(k)}, \quad (\text{G7})$$

where $\mathbf{z}^{(k+1)}$ is the preconditioned residual (see below) and β_k is chosen to enforce (G6):

$$\mathbf{p}^{(k)\top} A \mathbf{p}^{(k+1)} = 0 \Rightarrow \beta_k = -\frac{\mathbf{p}^{(k)\top} A \mathbf{z}^{(k+1)}}{\mathbf{p}^{(k)\top} A \mathbf{p}^{(k)}}.$$

Using the residual-update identity $\mathbf{r}^{(k+1)} = \mathbf{r}^{(k)} - \alpha_k A \mathbf{p}^{(k)}$, a standard manipulation (Shewchuk, 1994) rewrites β_k in the
775 form in Algorithm 1:

$$\beta_k = \frac{\langle \mathbf{r}^{(k+1)}, \mathbf{z}^{(k+1)} \rangle}{\langle \mathbf{r}^{(k)}, \mathbf{z}^{(k)} \rangle}. \quad (\text{G8})$$

G5 Preconditioning

Apply \mathbb{M}^{-1} to the residual to get

$$\mathbf{z}^{(k)} = \mathbb{M}^{-1} \mathbf{r}^{(k)}. \quad (\text{G9})$$

780 The preconditioned algorithm operates as if on the transformed system

$$(\mathbb{M}^{-1/2} A \mathbb{M}^{-1/2})(\mathbb{M}^{1/2} \phi) = \mathbb{M}^{-1/2} \mathbf{c}. \quad (\text{G10})$$

If $\mathbb{M}^{-1/2} A \mathbb{M}^{-1/2}$ has a smaller condition number than A alone, PCG converges faster. The art of preconditioning lies in choosing \mathbb{M} that (i) approximates A well, (ii) is SPD itself, and (iii) is cheap to solve.

G6 Convergence bound

785 The classical bound for CG applied to SPD A (exact arithmetic) is (Golub and Van Loan, 2013)

$$\|\phi^{(k)} - \phi^*\|_A \leq 2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\kappa(A)} - 1}{\sqrt{\kappa(A)} + 1} \right)^k \|\phi^{(0)} - \phi^*\|_A, \quad (\text{G11})$$

where $\kappa(A) = \lambda_{\max}(A)/\lambda_{\min}(A)$ is the condition number and $\phi^* = A^{-1} \mathbf{c}$ is the exact solution. Iteration count to reduce the error by a factor of ϵ therefore scales as

$$k_\epsilon \lesssim \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\kappa(A)} \log(2/\epsilon).$$

790 For the discrete Laplacian on a quasi-uniform mesh of characteristic spacing h , the condition number grows as $\kappa(A) \sim h^{-2}$, so PCG iteration count grows as h^{-1} — the iteration-count growth anticipated in the parallel-performance design of the main text (§8). At fixed vertical grid under horizontal-only refinement, $N \propto h^{-2}$, so this growth is $\mathcal{O}(N^{1/2})$.

G7 Preconditioners: two implemented, one planned

G7.1 None ($\mathbb{M} = \mathbf{I}$).

795 Straight CG. Used as a baseline reference.

G7.2 Jacobi ($\mathbb{M} = \mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(A)$).

Per iteration, for each $n = (i, k)$:

$$z_n = D_{nn}^{-1} r_n = \frac{r_n}{|L_{nn}|}.$$

Cost: one division per cell-column per iteration. Cheap. Reduces condition number by a modest constant factor but does not
800 change the $\kappa \sim h^{-2}$ scaling.

G7.3 Block symmetric Gauss–Seidel (planned).

Within each MPI rank p , let \mathcal{I}_p denote the rank’s owned cells (no halo). Define the triangular splittings

$$A|_{\mathcal{I}_p} = L_p + D_p + U_p,$$

with D_p the rank- p diagonal and L_p, U_p the strictly lower and upper triangular parts (under the cell-column ordering). The
805 block SGS preconditioner is

$$\mathbb{M}^{-1} = (D_p + U_p)^{-1} D_p (D_p + L_p)^{-1},$$

applied block-Jacobi across ranks (no coupling between ranks inside \mathbb{M}^{-1}). It is SPD: since A is symmetric, $U_p = L_p^T$, so the
preconditioner factors as $\mathbb{M} = (D_p + L_p) D_p^{-1} (D_p + L_p)^T$ — a congruence of the positive diagonal D_p^{-1} by the nonsingular
triangular factor $D_p + L_p$. Cost per iteration: two triangular solves (forward + backward sweep) plus one halo exchange. This
810 preconditioner is specified here but is not implemented in the current code; it is planned as future work.

G8 Termination criterion

Algorithm 1 terminates when $\|\mathbf{r}^{(k)}\|_2 / \|\mathbf{c}\|_2 < \text{tol}$. Note that (G11) bounds the A -norm of the error, while the stopping test
sees only the residual. With $\mathbf{r}^{(k)} = A(\phi^* - \phi^{(k)})$, the two are related by

$$\lambda_{\max}^{-1} \|\mathbf{r}^{(k)}\|_2^2 \leq \|\phi^{(k)} - \phi^*\|_A^2 = \mathbf{r}^{(k)T} A^{-1} \mathbf{r}^{(k)} \leq \lambda_{\min}^{-1} \|\mathbf{r}^{(k)}\|_2^2,$$

815 so a small residual guarantees a small A -norm error only up to the factor $\lambda_{\min}^{-1/2}$, and the relative ℓ^2 error is controlled by the
relative residual only up to a factor $\kappa(A)$. The relative-residual criterion is nonetheless used as a simple, inexpensive heuristic;
at $\text{tol} = 10^{-8}$ the algebraic error is far below the discretization error in all experiments reported in the main text.

Appendix H: Edge-normal and cell-centered E-field reconstruction

H1 Edge-normal component

820 From $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi$ and the edge-normal finite-difference gradient (C5), the edge-normal \mathbf{E} component at edge e between cells i and $j = \text{nbr}(i, e)$ is

$$E_n^{(e,k)} = -(\nabla\phi) \cdot \mathbf{n}_e \approx -\frac{\phi_{j,k} - \phi_{i,k}}{d_e}. \quad (\text{H1})$$

This is stored in the Registry field `E_normal`.

H2 Cell-centered vector reconstruction

825 To reconstruct the full vector \mathbf{E} at cell centers, we use MPAS's existing radial-basis-function (RBF) machinery in `mpas_rbf_interpolat`. This machinery takes a set of edge-normal values and, for each cell i , fits a 3-component vector \mathbf{E}_i such that for each edge $e \in \partial i$:

$$\mathbf{E}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_e \approx E_n^{(e,k)}. \quad (\text{H2})$$

The fit is a linear map built from the cell's edge geometry plus a set of RBF coefficients precomputed at mesh init. The coefficients are mesh-only and do not depend on ϕ : they are computed once and stored. The reconstruction call at each time step is therefore a matrix-vector product of fixed small dimension (12–24 for a typical hexagonal cell) per cell.

The same machinery is used to reconstruct cell-centered velocity vectors from edge-normal momentum in the MPAS dynamics core; full details are given in Skamarock et al. (2012) and Ringler et al. (2010).

H3 Output to Registry

835 The reconstructed vector is written to the Registry field `E_vector` with dimensions `(R3, nVertLevels, nCells)`. The vector is expressed in the model's Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z ECEF-style on the sphere, or flat Cartesian for doubly periodic configurations). A user may derive the magnitude $|\mathbf{E}|$ from `E_vector` in post-processing.

Appendix I: Implementation note: volume-integrated vs per-unit-volume form

This appendix compares two mathematically equivalent forms of the discrete operator and documents the one chosen for
840 implementation.

I1 Two equivalent forms

I1.1 Form I: volume-integrated.

$\mathbb{L}_I \phi = \mathbf{b}_I$ with

$$(\mathbb{L}_I \phi)_{i,k} = \sum_e \varepsilon \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_j - \phi_i) + \varepsilon A_i \left[\frac{\phi_{k+1} - \phi_k}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}} + \frac{\phi_{k-1} - \phi_k}{\Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}} \right], \quad (11)$$

$$845 \quad b_{I,i,k} = -\rho_{i,k} V_{i,k}. \quad (12)$$

\mathbb{L}_I is symmetric in standard ℓ^2 inner product (Appendix E). CG uses standard inner products and norms: $\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle = \sum_n u_n v_n$.

I1.2 Form II: per-unit-volume.

$\mathbb{L}_{II} \phi = \mathbf{b}_{II}$ with

$$(\mathbb{L}_{II} \phi)_{i,k} = \frac{1}{V_{i,k}} (\mathbb{L}_I \phi)_{i,k}, \quad (13)$$

$$850 \quad b_{II,i,k} = -\rho_{i,k}. \quad (14)$$

\mathbb{L}_{II} is *not* symmetric in standard ℓ^2 because the diagonal scaling by $V_{i,k}^{-1}$ breaks symmetry at the matrix level. It is, however, symmetric in the volume-weighted inner product $\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_V = \sum_n V_n u_n v_n$:

$$\langle \mathbb{L}_{II} \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_V = \sum_n V_n \cdot (\mathbb{L}_I \mathbf{u})_n / V_n \cdot v_n = \sum_n (\mathbb{L}_I \mathbf{u})_n v_n = \langle \mathbb{L}_I \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_{\ell^2},$$

and similarly $\langle \mathbf{u}, \mathbb{L}_{II} \mathbf{v} \rangle_V = \langle \mathbb{L}_I \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} \rangle_{\ell^2} = \langle \mathbb{L}_I \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_{\ell^2}$ (since \mathbb{L}_I is ℓ^2 -symmetric). CG in form II uses V -weighted inner products

855 and norms throughout.

I1.3 Equivalence.

Both forms solve the same continuous PDE to the same order. The two systems have identical solutions ϕ . The choice of form affects how the matrix and the inner products are expressed in code but not the mathematical result.

I2 This paper uses Form I

860 The main text and previous appendices use Form I throughout, because:

1. Form I's matrix is ℓ^2 -symmetric, so the generic CG algorithm in Algorithm 1 applies with no modification.
2. The symmetry proof in Appendix E is direct and constructive.
3. Form I's right-hand side is $-\rho V_{i,k}$, which is physically interpretable as total charge in the cell.

Form II is a valid alternative but introduces the bookkeeping of a V -weighted inner product and is less transparent pedagogically.

865

I3 Which form the implementation uses

The implementation adopts **Form I**. With Form I, all CG code operates in standard ℓ^2 inner products (no V -weighted variants needed), the matrix is transparently symmetric, and the right-hand side $b = -\rho \cdot V_{i,k}$ has the physical interpretation of total charge in the cell-column.

870 Concretely, Form I fixes the stored operator weights as:

– $\text{h_weight}(k, e) = \varepsilon \cdot \ell_e \cdot \Delta z_k / d_e$ — a 2D array over $(\text{nVertLevels}, \text{nEdges})$ because Δz_k depends on k (and, on terrain-following meshes, on i as well),

– $\text{v_weight_upper}(k, i) = \varepsilon \cdot A_i / \Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}$, zero at $k = K$ under the Neumann top condition,

875 – $\text{v_weight_lower}(k, i) = \varepsilon \cdot A_i / \Delta z_{k-\frac{1}{2}}$ for $k > 1$ and $= \varepsilon \cdot A_i / (\frac{1}{2} \Delta z_1)$ at $k = 1$ to represent the ground-Dirichlet face.

The matvec for row (i, k) assembles the sum of face-flux contributions directly from these weights and returns $A\phi$ where $A \equiv -\mathbb{L}$ is the SPD negated Laplacian used inside the CG iteration.

Appendix J: Exterior-calculus formulation

880 This appendix recasts the continuous and discrete problems in the language of differential forms and discrete exterior calculus (DEC). The main text and the earlier appendices treat ϕ as a scalar function on a Euclidean domain, $\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi$ as a vector field, and the discrete operator as a matrix assembled from mesh metrics. The exterior-calculus perspective is equivalent, coordinate-free, and makes several features of the TRiSK construction transparent at the level of *structure* rather than *coefficients*:

– The continuous Poisson problem is a single equation on the de Rham complex: $\delta(\varepsilon d\phi) = \rho\mu$, where μ is the volume form.

885 – The TRiSK div-of-grad discretization is the composition $d^\top H d$ with H a *diagonal* Hodge-star matrix.

– H is diagonal precisely because the MPAS mesh is a *circumcentric Voronoi–Delaunay pair*: primal edges are orthogonal to their corresponding dual edges. This structural property is what makes the TRiSK operators mimetic.

– Symmetry and positive-definiteness of the assembled operator follow from the factorization $d^\top H d$ with H SPD, without any coefficient-level calculation.

890 – Discrete Stokes’ theorem, $d^2 = 0$ at the chain level, and integration-by-parts all hold as *identities*, not approximations.

The material below is self-contained but assumes comfort with the vector-calculus / divergence-theorem derivations in Appendices C–D.

J1 Continuous setup: differential forms on the atmosphere

Let $M \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ denote the atmospheric domain, a three-dimensional oriented Riemannian manifold with boundary $\partial M = \Gamma_g \cup \Gamma_{\text{top}} \cup \Gamma_{\text{lat}}$. Write $\Omega^k(M)$ for the space of smooth k -forms on M . The de Rham complex is the sequence

$$\Omega^0(M) \xrightarrow{d} \Omega^1(M) \xrightarrow{d} \Omega^2(M) \xrightarrow{d} \Omega^3(M), \quad (\text{J1})$$

where d is the exterior derivative, satisfying $d^2 = 0$. Under the Euclidean metric, Ω^0 is identified with scalar fields, Ω^1 with vector fields (via the musical isomorphism \flat), Ω^2 with vector fields (via \flat after Hodge-duality), and Ω^3 with scalar fields (as volume densities). Under these identifications:

$$900 \quad d : \Omega^0 \rightarrow \Omega^1 \leftrightarrow \nabla, \quad (\text{J2})$$

$$d : \Omega^1 \rightarrow \Omega^2 \leftrightarrow \nabla \times, \quad (\text{J3})$$

$$d : \Omega^2 \rightarrow \Omega^3 \leftrightarrow \nabla \cdot. \quad (\text{J4})$$

The Hodge star $\star : \Omega^k \rightarrow \Omega^{n-k}$ (with $n = 3$) uses the metric and the volume form $\mu \in \Omega^n$ to identify forms with their duals. The codifferential $\delta : \Omega^k \rightarrow \Omega^{k-1}$ is defined by

$$905 \quad \delta = (-1)^{n(k+1)+1} \star d \star. \quad (\text{J5})$$

On $n = 3$ for $k = 1$, $\delta = -\star d \star$, which under the form-to-vector identification corresponds to $-\nabla \cdot$ on vector fields.

J2 Continuous Poisson as a de Rham equation

Poisson's equation $\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon \nabla \phi) = -\rho$ becomes, under the identifications above:

$$\delta(\varepsilon d\phi) = \rho, \quad \phi \in \Omega^0(M). \quad (\text{J6})$$

910 Equivalently, multiplying by μ to view ρ as a 3-form $\rho\mu \in \Omega^3$,

$$d\star(\varepsilon d\phi) = -\rho\mu. \quad (\text{J7})$$

This is the form in which the equation will be discretized below: $d\phi$ is a 1-form, $\star(\varepsilon d\phi)$ is a 2-form (representing a flux), and $d\star(\varepsilon d\phi)$ is a 3-form (a volume density) that must equal $-\rho\mu$.

J3 Boundary conditions in form language

915 The present boundary conditions translate as:

$$\phi|_{\Gamma_g} = 0 \quad (0\text{-form Dirichlet trace}), \quad (\text{J8})$$

$$\iota_{\Gamma_{\text{top}}}^* \star(\varepsilon d\phi) = 0 \quad (2\text{-form flux trace; Neumann}), \quad (\text{J9})$$

where ι_{Γ}^* denotes pullback of a form to the boundary surface Γ . The top-face Neumann condition is a flux-trace vanishing condition on the 2-form $\star(\varepsilon d\phi)$, which is the natural (i.e., Neumann-type) boundary datum for the second-order elliptic operator

920 in (J6).

J4 Discrete setup: the cochain complex on MPAS's mesh

The MPAS domain is tiled by a three-dimensional cell complex \mathcal{K} built as the extrusion of a planar Voronoi tessellation in the horizontal by a stack of K vertical layers. The primal cell complex \mathcal{K} has:

Primal 0-cells	vertices of the extruded mesh
Primal 1-cells	edges (vertical edges + horizontal Voronoi edges)
Primal 2-cells	faces (lateral faces of the prism + horizontal caps)
Primal 3-cells	prisms (Voronoi cell \times layer)

925 The *dual* complex $\star\mathcal{K}$ is defined by placing a dual 0-cell at each cell-column center (the Voronoi generator in the horizontal, the layer midpoint in the vertical) and taking the dual 1-cells to be segments between adjacent dual 0-cells, passing through the center of the corresponding primal 2-face. Dual 2-cells are polygons orthogonal to primal 1-edges, and dual 3-cells are dual volumes around primal 0-vertices.

The scalar potential ϕ is carried at dual 0-cells (cell centers): a *dual 0-cochain*. The integer dimension

$$930 \quad N = n_{\text{cells}} \cdot K \tag{J10}$$

equals the number of dual 0-cells, i.e., the number of unknowns.

J4.1 Cochain spaces and pairings.

Let C^k denote the space of real-valued primal k -cochains (functions on primal k -cells) and \tilde{C}^k the space of dual k -cochains. Pairings $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_k$ are integration-like sums over cells.

935 J4.2 Coboundary operators.

The discrete exterior derivative at level k is the coboundary operator

$$d_k : C^k \rightarrow C^{k+1}, \quad (d_k \alpha)(\sigma) = \sum_{\tau \in \partial \sigma} [\sigma : \tau] \alpha(\tau), \tag{J11}$$

where σ is a $(k+1)$ -cell, $\partial \sigma$ is its boundary as a formal chain of k -cells, and $[\sigma : \tau] \in \{-1, +1\}$ is the orientation coefficient.

The matrix representation of d_k is the signed incidence matrix of $(k+1)$ -cells on k -cells. The fundamental identity

$$940 \quad d_{k+1} \circ d_k = 0 \tag{J12}$$

holds *exactly* at the chain level (no mesh-refinement error), by the same combinatorial argument as $\partial^2 = 0$ on simplicial chains.

J5 Discrete gradient on dual 0-cochains

The unknown ϕ is a dual 0-cochain, i.e., a function $\tilde{\phi} : \{\text{cell columns}\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. By duality the dual coboundary operator $\tilde{d}_0 : \tilde{C}^0 \rightarrow \tilde{C}^1$ acts on cell-center values to produce values on dual 1-cells:

$$945 \quad (\tilde{d}_0 \tilde{\phi})(\tilde{e}) = \phi_j - \phi_i, \tag{J13}$$

where \tilde{e} is the dual 1-cell connecting cell centers i and j , oriented from i to j .

This is the discrete analogue of $d\phi$ on a 0-form. It carries only the *combinatorial* content of the gradient; the geometric content (how the gradient is measured on the ground) enters only through the Hodge star (§J6).

A primal 1-edge e pierces exactly one dual 2-face, which is in bijection with one dual 1-edge \tilde{e} . Under this bijection the
 950 primal edge length ℓ_e and the dual edge length $\tilde{\ell}_e = d_e$ are the two relevant geometric quantities associated with edge e .

J6 Discrete Hodge star on MPAS's circumcentric mesh

The discrete Hodge star $H_k : C^k \rightarrow \tilde{C}^{n-k}$ maps primal k -cochains to dual $(n-k)$ -cochains via local integration over dual cells. The central structural fact of DEC on orthogonal primal–dual meshes is:

Diagonal Hodge star theorem. On a mesh where every primal k -cell σ is *orthogonal* to its dual $(n-k)$ -cell $\star\sigma$ (in
 955 the sense that every primal edge is orthogonal to the corresponding dual face, and every primal face is orthogonal to the corresponding dual edge), the discrete Hodge star H_k is diagonal with respect to the natural cochain bases, with entries $(H_k)_{\sigma\sigma} = |\star\sigma|/|\sigma|$.

MPAS's extruded Voronoi mesh satisfies this orthogonality *exactly*:

- In the horizontal, the primal 1-edge e is a Voronoi face edge, perpendicular by construction to the line segment between
 960 cell centers (the dual 1-edge through e).
- In the vertical, primal edges are vertical by assumption (flat terrain), and layer faces are horizontal; orthogonality is automatic.

We need the star acting on dual 1-cochains, mapping them to primal 2-cochains — the dual-to-primal counterpart of the boxed statement, with the same measure-ratio entries $|\star\tilde{\sigma}|/|\tilde{\sigma}|$ read with $\tilde{\sigma}$ a dual 1-cell and $\star\tilde{\sigma}$ the primal 2-face it pierces.

965 We keep the symbol H_1 for this diagonal matrix. Its diagonal entries at dual 1-edge \tilde{e} / pierced primal 2-face e are:

- Lateral prism face at horizontal edge e — a primal 2-face of width ℓ_e and layer thickness Δz_k , area $\ell_e \Delta z_k$ — pierced by the dual 1-edge of length d_e joining the two cell-column centers.

$$(H_1)_{\tilde{e}e}^{(\text{horiz, layer } k)} = \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e}. \quad (\text{J14})$$

- Horizontal cap at the upper face of layer k — a primal 2-face of area A_i — pierced by the vertical dual 1-edge of length
 970 $\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}$ joining the two layer midpoints.

$$(H_1)_{\tilde{e}e}^{(\text{vert, upper})} = \frac{A_i}{\Delta z_{k+\frac{1}{2}}}. \quad (\text{J15})$$

Analogously for the lower vertical face. These diagonal entries are *exactly* the mesh-dependent weights $h_{\text{weight}}(k, e)/\varepsilon$ and $v_{\text{weight}_\uparrow}(k, i)/\varepsilon$ of the implementation (see Appendix I). The correspondence is not a coincidence — the TRiSK construction is exactly the DEC discretization of $\delta \circ (\varepsilon d \cdot)$ on the circumcentric Voronoi–Delaunay pair.

975 **J7 TRiSK div-of-grad as $\mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{d}$**

Applying the discrete analogues of (J6) to the cell-centered potential $\tilde{\phi}$:

$$(-\mathbb{L})\tilde{\phi} = \varepsilon \cdot \mathbf{d}_0^\top \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{d}_0 \tilde{\phi}, \quad (\text{J16})$$

where \mathbf{d}_0 is (J13) (the discrete dual gradient $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_0$; the tilde is dropped from here on), \mathbf{H}_1 is the diagonal Hodge star (J14)–(J15), and \mathbf{d}_0^\top is its matrix transpose (which represents the adjoint coboundary, i.e., the discrete divergence). The permittivity ε factors out as an overall scalar because it is constant in the present configuration; for variable ε it is absorbed into \mathbf{H}_1 as an edge-dependent factor.

J7.1 Unwinding the composition row by row.

For a cell i , the row $\tilde{\phi} \mapsto (\mathbf{d}_0^\top \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{d}_0 \tilde{\phi})_i$ expands as

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{d}_0^\top \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{d}_0 \tilde{\phi})_i &= \sum_{\tilde{e} \in \partial^\top(i)} [i : \tilde{e}] (\mathbf{H}_1)_{\tilde{e}\tilde{e}} (\mathbf{d}_0 \tilde{\phi})(\tilde{e}) \\ &= \sum_{\tilde{e}: e \in \partial i} [i : \tilde{e}] \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_j - \phi_i) \\ &= \sum_{e \in \partial i} \frac{\ell_e \Delta z_k}{d_e} (\phi_i - \phi_j) \quad (\text{using } [i : \tilde{e}] = -1 \text{ for } \tilde{e} \text{ oriented from } i \text{ to } j) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{J17})$$

plus the analogous vertical-face terms. Comparing to the volume-integrated stencil derived in Appendix C, eq. (C7), the two expressions agree identically — the overall sign difference is exactly the $-\mathbb{L}$ on the left-hand side of (J16).

Thus:

$$990 \quad A = -\mathbb{L} = \varepsilon \cdot \mathbf{d}_0^\top \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{d}_0. \quad (\text{J18})$$

The ground-Dirichlet boundary condition is imposed by removing the ground face from the primal 2-chain in the definition of \mathbf{d}_0 and adding the ground-face Hodge-star contribution to the diagonal of A , equivalent to the half-distance ground-face entry of $v_{\text{weight}_\downarrow}(1, i)$.

J8 Structural symmetry and positive-definiteness

995 From the factorization $A = \varepsilon \mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{d}$:

J8.1 Symmetry.

Transposition gives $A^\top = \varepsilon \mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{H}^\top \mathbf{d}$. Since \mathbf{H} is diagonal, $\mathbf{H}^\top = \mathbf{H}$, so $A^\top = A$.

J8.2 Positive semi-definiteness.

For any \mathbf{u} ,

$$1000 \quad \mathbf{u}^\top A \mathbf{u} = \varepsilon \mathbf{u}^\top \mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{d} \mathbf{u} = \varepsilon (\mathbf{d} \mathbf{u})^\top \mathbf{H} (\mathbf{d} \mathbf{u}) \geq 0, \quad (\text{J19})$$

since H is diagonal with positive entries. This is the DEC form of Dirichlet's principle.

J8.3 Strict positive-definiteness under ground Dirichlet.

Equality in (J19) holds iff $d\mathbf{u} = 0$, i.e., iff \mathbf{u} is a discrete constant. The ground-Dirichlet condition removes the constant mode from the admissible space (any vector with $v_{i,1} \neq 0$ has a nonzero ground-face contribution to $\mathbf{u}^\top A\mathbf{u}$), so $\mathbf{u}^\top A\mathbf{u} > 0$ for
 1005 nonzero admissible \mathbf{u} . Hence A is SPD.

The pair-by-pair entry comparison of Appendix E is therefore subsumed by a two-line structural argument in DEC language.

J9 Mimetic identities

Several identities that are approximations in coefficient-level calculations hold exactly at the cochain level:

J9.1 Curl–grad vanishing.

1010 $d_1 d_0 = 0$ combinatorially. Consequence for MPAS: the discrete curl of a gradient is exactly zero, not $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$.

J9.2 Div–curl vanishing.

$d_2 d_1 = 0$ combinatorially. Consequence: the discrete divergence of a curl vanishes exactly.

J9.3 Discrete Stokes' theorem.

For any primal k -chain c and primal k -cochain α ,

$$1015 \quad \langle d\alpha, c \rangle = \langle \alpha, \partial c \rangle \tag{J20}$$

exactly, by the definition of the coboundary d as the dual of the boundary ∂ . Applied to the divergence stencil, this is discrete integration by parts: the sum of fluxes out of a cell equals minus the sum of fluxes into neighboring cells, with the shared edge contributing equally to both sides. This was verified coefficient-level in §C4; the DEC statement makes it structural.

J9.4 Integration-by-parts for the Laplacian.

1020 For admissible \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} (satisfying the Dirichlet BC),

$$\mathbf{u}^\top A\mathbf{v} = \varepsilon(d\mathbf{u})^\top H(d\mathbf{v}) = \varepsilon(d\mathbf{v})^\top H(d\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{v}^\top A\mathbf{u}, \tag{J21}$$

which is the discrete form of Green's first identity.

J10 Convergence from the DEC perspective

The structural advantage of the DEC discretization is that *combinatorial* identities like $d^2 = 0$ and adjointness hold exactly, so
 1025 the discretization error is concentrated entirely in the *Hodge star*. Intuitively: the mesh's combinatorial content is always right, and the geometric content is right to the extent that H approximates the continuous Hodge.

On a circumcentric Voronoi–Delaunay pair with quasi-uniform cell sizes, the diagonal Hodge star (J14) is second-order accurate as an approximation to the continuous \star . Since the coboundary (J13) is exact at the cochain level, the composition $d^\top Hd$ inherits the Hodge star’s accuracy and yields an $\mathcal{O}(h^2)$ approximation of the continuous Laplacian in L^2 under mesh-regularity assumptions (Hirani, 2003).
1030

On distorted or variable-resolution meshes, the quality of the diagonal Hodge-star approximation degrades. Primal–dual orthogonality itself is exact for any Voronoi–Delaunay pair — Voronoi faces are perpendicular bisectors of the generator segments — so what is lost is not orthogonality but *centering*: the generator segment no longer crosses the shared face at its midpoint, generators drift from cell centroids, and the one-point measure ratios (J14) sample the flux off-center. The DEC framework thus predicts that convergence-rate losses on distorted meshes track the geometric off-centering of the primal–dual pair. This prediction motivates the well-centeredness and cell-size-gradient correlation analysis of the mesh-sensitivity study in the main text (§7).
1035

J11 Connection to finite element exterior calculus

Finite element exterior calculus (FEEC) is the Galerkin/variational counterpart of DEC (Arnold et al., 2006). Using Whitney forms (piecewise polynomial differential forms compatible with the de Rham complex) on a simplicial triangulation, FEEC produces a Galerkin discretization of (J6) that is structurally similar to the DEC formulation above.
1040

On the Delaunay triangulation associated with MPAS’s Voronoi mesh, the lowest-order Whitney 0-forms are piecewise-linear nodal elements (P1), Whitney 1-forms are lowest-order Nédélec edge elements (Bossavit, 1998), and so on. The *mass-lumped* Galerkin discretization of $\delta(\varepsilon d\phi) = \rho$ using these Whitney spaces coincides with the DEC formulation when the mass matrices are replaced by diagonal lumped approximations, and these lumped mass matrices coincide with the diagonal Hodge stars of (J14)–(J15) on circumcentric Voronoi–Delaunay pairs.
1045

This observation provides two complementary characterizations of TRiSK’s elliptic operator:

1. As a *DEC discretization* on the Voronoi–Delaunay complex, with closed-form diagonal Hodge stars derived from mesh metrics;
- 1050 2. As a *lumped-mass Galerkin FEEC discretization* on the Delaunay triangulation using lowest-order Whitney elements, with mass lumping justified by the orthogonality of the circumcentric pair.

The two views are equivalent on well-centered circumcentric meshes, but diverge when well-centering fails. This is the deep reason why MPAS meshes are required to be “well-centered” — each Delaunay triangle contains its circumcenter, i.e., each Voronoi corner lies inside its dual triangle, so all signed dual lengths are positive — for the operators to behave well.

1055 J12 Summary

Reading the implementation (Appendices C and I) in DEC language:

Code quantity	DEC interpretation
ϕ at cell centers	dual 0-cochain $\tilde{\phi}$
$\phi_j - \phi_i$ at edge	$(\mathbf{d}_0 \tilde{\phi})(\tilde{e})$
$h_{\text{weight}}(k, e)/\varepsilon$	$(\mathbf{H}_1)_{\tilde{e}\tilde{e}}$ (horizontal)
$v_{\text{weight}_\uparrow}(k, i)/\varepsilon$	$(\mathbf{H}_1)_{\tilde{e}\tilde{e}}$ (vertical)
Matvec $A\tilde{\phi}$	$\varepsilon \mathbf{d}_0^\top \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{d}_0 \tilde{\phi}$
Right-hand side $\mathbf{c} = \rho \cdot V$ of $A\phi = \mathbf{c}$	the 3-form $\rho\mu$ integrated over primal 3-cells
Ground-face weight $v_{\text{weight}_\downarrow}(1, i)$	ground-face Hodge entry retained with Dirichlet datum $\phi_g = 0$
$-\mathbb{L}$ SPD	factorization $\mathbf{d}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{d}$ with \mathbf{H} SPD

1060 The exterior-calculus formulation adds no computational content that is not already in the coefficient-level implementation, but it gives clean structural reasons for the properties proven combinatorially in the other appendices: mesh-centric *design choices* (e.g., insisting on circumcentric meshes, embracing the Voronoi–Delaunay pair as the primal–dual complex) become *consequences* of demanding a diagonal Hodge star that makes the DEC operators computationally efficient.

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